

Kei Chappe.

A Multimodal Analysis of Swiss-German Internet Memes

Master's Thesis
by
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Bern Academy of the Arts
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Abstract

Internet memes have become a way of communicating online and a significant cultural phenomenon.

This research project addresses a lack of research on Swiss meme culture, building on previous research in the field of meme studies. It presents a systematic analysis of multimodality, language use and vernacular playfulness evident in Swiss image-based internet memes. The research focuses on unraveling how Swiss-German, a primarily spoken vernacular, is used in memes.

Quantitative content analysis was deployed on randomized samples of the corpus to develop a typology of language use in Swiss-German memes. Specimens of each type were analysed using qualitative multimodal discourse analysis. The corpus analysed for this study consists of image-based memes posted on Instagram “meme pages” in 2020 and 2021. During this year of Switzerland’s COVID-19 lockdown, an active subculture of Swiss meme creators had formed on Instagram.

The findings of the study reveal the influence of African-American Vernacular English on Swiss meme culture, the use of visual distortion as a communication mode and the highly ironic and literary use of written Swiss-German dialect. The study is one of the first systematic accounts of Swiss meme culture and highlights how local Swiss-German dialects and multimodal communication are used creatively and ironically in Swiss meme culture.

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Respect is due to all the inventors and propagators of new slang and expressions, and of course, the meme page administrators of Instagram.

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Figure 1)
 “Knorrli” meme,
 @souhuendin,
 16 March 2021

Figure 2)
 “Globi” meme,
 @chline_hutzu,
 8 March 2021

Figure 3)
 “Gölä” meme,
 @znueninaehmems,
 23 October 2020

1. Introduction

If it exists, there is a meme of it¹.

Billionaires launching themselves into space, Bulgarian pop songs, Canadian rappers, cartoon characters, corporate mascots, crustaceans, domestic animals, folklore, gender, Ghanaian burial rites, gossip, identity, mental health, movie scenes, news headlines, pandemics, Plato, politicians, politician's hairstyles, politics, sandwiches, sculptures, Silicon Valley technology, slang, slips of the tongue, that awkward date, war crimes, work: *everything* can be and is *memed*. Did an event even happen, if there is no meme of it? Internet memes do not only reflect everyday life, they are, for many people, an integral part of it. Internet memes are a way - a *mode* - of talking about, commenting on and framing things online, constituting the *lingua franca*² (Milner, 2016) and post-modern, *digital folklore* (Shifman, 2013b) of the internet. Even if you do not actively follow meme culture: if you have spent any time online, you will have come in touch with memetic media in the form of text, image or video. Following memes is like tapping into a public conversation. A look through the memetic keyhole offers insights into current affairs, politics, culture and, vitally, into how language is used online.

In this master's thesis, I investigate the use of Swiss-German and multimodal communication in Swiss meme culture. A very active local meme subculture has developed on Instagram during Switzerland's COVID-19 lockdown in 2020 and 2021. The output of the subculture is largely oriented towards global and American memetic conventions. At the same time, it is firmly rooted in a local context through its use of Swiss-German dialects and Swiss iconography in the form of company mascots, cartoon characters and musicians such as Knorrli³ (Figure 1), Globi⁴ (Figure 2) and Gölä⁵ (Figure 3). Throughout this thesis, I will discuss the (contested) folkloric nature of memes and highlight the importance of that "fundamental memetic logic" (Milner, 2016) of multimodality. Furthermore, I will compare Swiss-German use in memes to language use in advertisement and contemporary literary writing. My research into Swiss-German image memes shared on Instagram is

¹ Adapted from the infamous internet adage "If it exists, there is porn of it" ('Rule 34', 2024)

² "Any language used for communication between groups who have no other language in common" (Matthews, 2014)

³ The Swiss company mascot of German food and beverage brand Knorr; the makers of that essential ingredient of Swiss cuisine, "Aromat" ('Knorr (Brand)', 2023; 'Knorr's Geschichte', 2024). The meme by @souhuendin is captioned "DAMN knorrli sure got THICC", using an African-American loan word discussed later.

⁴ "Globi is a Swiss cartoon character occasionally referred to as Switzerland's Mickey Mouse" ('Globi', 2023). The caption of the meme by @chline_hutzu translates to "Monday. New week, new luck. Wishing you a all a great day and a successful new week".

⁵ A popular Swiss rock musician, performing mainly in Bernese dialect ('Gölä', 2023). "Huärä schiss bürogiglä" can be translated as "stupid ass office workers".

Figure 4)
 "Migros" poster,
 photo by author, 2023

Figure 5)
 "Coop" in-store poster,
 photo by author, 2023

Figure 6)
 "Triggerre" shitpost,
 @srfarchiv,
 1 November 2023

guided by my main research question: How is Swiss-German used in Swiss meme culture?

1.1 Mundart-Mutations¹ in Public Relations and Advertisement

Swiss-German, encompassing the many Swiss-German dialects, is not a primarily written language. In formal, professional, and educational settings, *Hochdeutsch* (“high German”) is used, also referred to as the *Schriftsprache*, the “written language”. Due to the advanced digitalization of Swiss society, especially the proliferation of text messaging, writing in Swiss-German has become a popular practice. Karina Frick, a linguistics professor at the University of Zurich, states that young people have never written in dialect as much as they do today (‘Dialekt als Digilekt Mundartschreibung im Internet’, 2019; Dürscheid & Frick, 2016). Digital platforms and a lack of strict grammar and spelling rules on how to write in Swiss-German seemingly promote creativity.

Vernacular playfulness in internet memes coincides with an increased use of Swiss-German in more formal contexts such as literature, advertising, and journalism. The duopolistic Swiss grocery retailers Migros and Coop have recently used Swiss-German in their branding and advertisements, as has Swisscom, the country’s leading telecom provider.

In Figure 5, Coop is advertising *miuch u chäs* (milk and cheese), in written Bernese dialect. Meanwhile, Migros is claiming to “*macht meh für d’Schwiiz*” (“doing more for Switzerland”, Figure 4), on a poster campaign. At roughly the same time, Swisscom was multimodally mixing German, Swiss-German, and English on the same poster campaign (Figure 7). Below the Swisscom poster, another poster campaign by “GVB” (“Gebäudeversicherung Bern”), a Bern-based real estate insurer, is yelling, in capitalized letters, “DRÄCKS GLUNGGE SEICH NOMAL!”. This rather humorous and harmless expletive literally means “FILTH PUDDLE NONSENSE AGAIN!”. “Seich” could mean both nonsense and urine. It is a first hint at both the sometimes obscene forms of folkloric expression and the highly ironic use of Swiss-German in meme culture discussed later.

Corporate advertisement campaigns, mascots, and slogans, maybe not unintentionally, invite adaptation as memes. For example, the “*chli stinke muess es*” (“it has to stink a little”) slogan by Coop was memed as “*chli triggere muess es*” (“it has to trigger a little”) in an Instagram post on Swiss meme page² @srfarchiv (Figure 6).

Figure 6 demonstrates the circulation, referentiality, and reappropriation fundamental to memetic media, logics covered in the Theoretical Framework. GVB is not alone in using lighthearted, somewhat ironic Swiss-German obscenities in their public relations. The tabloid “Blick” often incorporates Swiss-German expressions in their instantly recognizable yellow posters. A Blick darling is the term “Grüsel”, especially the “Sex-Grüsel”, or in Figure 8, the elusive “Güsel-Grüsel”. A “Grüsel” denotes a dirty, depraved human being (‘Grüsel’, 2018) or in the case of the “Sex-Grüsel” a sexually deviant person or pervert. “Güsel” means trash.

¹ “Mundart” can be literally translated as “the way of the mouth”, meaning dialect or vernacular.

² A “meme page” is an Instagram account that mostly posts memes. “Compilation accounts” share memes found on the internet, while most of the accounts in my corpus create “original content”, i.e. their own memes.

Figure 7)
Advertisement campaigns by
GVB and Swisscom,
photo by author, 2023

Figure 8)
"Blick" headline poster,
photo by author, May 2023

Sexualverbrechen
in Bern -
Verdächtiger
festgenommen

Das ist der
Sexgrüsel von
Bern

Figure 9)
"Sexgrüsel" meme,
@smiggie_ballz69, April 2021

The yellow Blick poster contains two connections to Swiss-German meme culture. Firstly, an account that is part of the compiled corpus is named @sexgruesel, most likely in a nod to Blick's repeated use and popularization of the term. Unsurprisingly, Blick's use of the word has been memed, as Figure 9 demonstrates. The top text translates to "Sex crime in Bern – suspect arrested" and the bottom text says "This is the Sexgrüsel of Bern".

Secondly, the Blick poster features a reference to transgender rights and identity, which are a current "hot topic" of the US *Kulturkampf* ('Culture War', 2024). The headline states how a US corporate beer brewery has suffered a sales collapse because of a trans woman. Meme culture in general is highly US-centric (Milner, 2016), a finding shared by Shifman et al. (2014), who have called memes "secret agents of globalization" and Americanization. References to American pop culture and politics are frequent in Swiss meme culture.

Swiss memes and advertisements share a playful mixing of dialect (often used tongue-in-cheek), *Hochdeutsch*, and English. Multimodal communication is essential to both media: sloganistic text, emoji, photographs, illustrations, and graphic elements are used in both memes and advertisement. This is not surprising, as they can be understood as genres of digital graphic design.

Ironic use of dialect, language mixing and borrowing, multimodality and American "hot topics" are integral aspects of Swiss-German meme culture. Of course, the borrowing of English terms is not a new phenomenon, nor a Swiss phenomenon. It is worth looking at two countries neighboring Switzerland for comparison and further evidence of Americanization. In Germany, the "Langenscheidt Verlag"¹ is designating a *Jugendwort des Jahres* ("youth word of the year") since 2008. In 2023, out of the top ten "youth words", six were of English origin ('Jugendwort 2023 Das Sind Die Top 10', 2023). An English term, "goofy", was crowned as the winner. In 2022, the winner was "smash". Out of the top ten German *Jugendwörter* of the year 2022, five were English words. If we look south, at Italy, there are similar developments. The Telegraph has reported on "cringe" being "officially added to Italian lexicon" by the Accademia della Crusca, "the country's foremost language institute and stalwart guardians of Italian" (Squires, 2021). According to Squires (2021), Italians have started using Italianized variants of cringe, such as "cringissimo" and "cringiare". The Academia is documenting "new words" or "parole nuove" on their website ('Elenco Delle Parole Nuove', 2019), for example "whatsappare", "boomer" and "memare" – to meme. In an article by the Financial Times (Kazmin, 2023), the phenomenon was dubbed "fake English" or "inglese farlocco" by linguist Licia Corbolante (Corbolante, 2016).

In this thesis, you will find many examples of "inglese farlocco", creative and highly ironic translations and misappropriation of English in Swiss-German memes. By focusing on Swiss-German itself, I want to address a gap in research on Swiss meme culture.

¹ "A German publishing company that specializes in language reference works" such as dictionaries ('Langenscheidt', 2024).

1.2 Research Problem and Interest

As my Literature Review shows, there is barely any research on Swiss meme culture. Furthermore, the political aspects of internet memes have been covered extensively and repeatedly. Outside of Switzerland, internet memes have been studied and researched for over a decade. Internet memes are neither a “new” nor a particularly “niche” phenomenon. They are a product of digitalization and an essential part of online discourse and internet culture. Testament to their ubiquitous nature are studies such as Zannettou et al. (2018), which has focused on a corpus of 160 million image memes. Or take Valensise et al. (2021), a study of the evolution of 2 million memes.

I argue that it is important to study the phenomenon of internet memes as it “happens”. Trends and conventions in meme culture develop and mutate quickly. A lot of the products of meme culture are ephemeral and locked into corporately owned social media platforms. Memes offer valuable insight into the evolution of Swiss-German and the cultural influences acting on it. Furthermore, they allow “eavesdropping” on public discourse surrounding current affairs and historical events. Eminent meme scholars such as Shifman (2013b) and Phillips & Milner (2017) treat memes as post-modern, digital folklore. Why not afford them the same scholarly interest and scrutiny that more conventional forms of folklore are afforded?

With the research conducted for this thesis, I address the gap in research about Swiss meme culture. I will discuss the research gap and the existing journalistic and scholarly writing on Swiss meme culture in the Literature Review. The identified gap and the extensive coverage of political aspects have motivated me to focus my research interest on a specific Swiss aspect of Swiss meme culture: the use of Swiss-German. To give focus to my research interests, I have formulated three research questions.

1.3 Research Questions

RQ1: How is Swiss-German used in image-based internet memes posted on Instagram?

By addressing this main question, I will provide evidence about how language use in the analysed memes is influenced by the conventions, catchphrases, and vernacular of international meme culture. I hypothesize that categories of language use in Swiss memes can be identified by closer inspection of a larger number of memes, revealing different ways in which Swiss-German is used in memes.

RQ2: What types of memetic Swiss-German mutations can be identified?

The assumption that categories or types of language use can be identified in the corpus underpins my second research question. To describe how such types potentially diverge from spoken and other forms of written Swiss-German, I have dubbed them “mutations”¹.

¹ With a respectful tip of the proverbial Fedora to Richard Dawkins, whose “memetics” will be discussed in the Theoretical Framework.

RQ3: What modes of communication are used in Swiss-German internet memes?

To make sense of memes and their communicative purposes, multimodality is key. Swiss-German text is but one of many communicative modes present in image memes. What communicative modes are primarily used in image memes? I hypothesize that these communicative modes and their combinations affect language use.

1.4 Theoretical Assumptions

To address these questions, I will ground my research in literature and concepts by meme studies scholars such as Shifman (2013b), Milner (2016), Phillips & Milner (2017) and the recent Swiss contribution to the field by Nowotny & Reidy (2022). This grounding means that I treat memes as groups of multimodal, folkloristic digital artifacts, which differs from an understanding, rooted in evolutionary biology, of memes as “units of cultural transmission” analogous to genes (Dawkins, 2016). I will use linguistic terminology to define phenomena such as borrowing, language switching and loan translations.

Contemporary Swiss literature by De l’Horizon (2022), Oppliger (2018) and Frank (2023) will be used to draw comparisons of language use in memes with literary writing. I will review and discuss these texts in the Literature Review.

1.5 Research Methodology

In order to answer my research questions, I will use a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. I will carry out my research in three phases: 1) definition of criteria and compilation of the corpus; 2) quantitative content analysis on a randomized sample of the corpus to identify types of language use; and 3) qualitative multimodal discourse analysis on select examples of each identified type.

The overall corpus consists of 7428 image memes shared on Instagram between March 16, 2020 and March 16, 2021. The 34 meme accounts selected for the corpus were either active before the Swiss COVID-19 lockdown or became active within one year of it and were still active in 2023. Randomized samples of five memes per account will be analyzed, totaling 167 memes per sample. The corpus and the applied methods are described in detail in Research Design and Methodology, and the findings are documented in Results. In the following and concluding section of this introduction, I will provide a bird's-eye view of my thesis.

1.6 Thesis Roadmap

The Introduction establishes the focus and research interest of this thesis, namely Swiss-German use in memes posted on Instagram. Language use in memes is compared to multimodal communication and use of Swiss-German in advertising. The grounding of my research in the field of meme studies is established and the quantitative and qualitative methods are introduced.

The Literature Review covers the state of research and the research gap on Swiss meme culture. I follow up on a discussion on the treatment of memes as folklore by Milner, Shifman and

Thesis Roadmap

Figure 10)
Thesis Roadmap,
by author, February 2024

Nowotny & Reidy and provide examples pertaining to this topic from the corpus. In a second contextual framing, language use in Swiss-German memes is compared to language use in contemporary Swiss-German literature.

The Theoretical Framework is structured along the four layers of the qualitative analysis. The memetic layer addresses the history, definitions and logics of internet memes and makes a tentative distinction between memes and the genre of shitposting. The formal layer describes the grotesque and distorted aesthetic of some memes and delves into the concept of multimodality as discussed by Milner and Kress & Van Leeuwen. The social layer covers how memes “shadow” historic events and current affairs and how some people consume news primarily via memes. The linguistic layer covers Swiss-German and its properties as a vernacular with no official rules, and provides definitions for the concepts underpinning the typology of memes developed for this study: loan words, calques, literal translations and code switching. The influence of African-American English and hiphop culture on meme culture and the memes in the corpus is addressed. A short summary of the key ideas and concepts is provided.

In Research Design and Methodology, the criteria for corpus selection are described and the reasoning for focusing on memes posted during the year of the Swiss COVID-19 lockdown is explained. Quantitative content analysis and qualitative multimodal discourse analysis are described, and how they are combined to perform an image type analysis. The typology of “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Loan Words”, “Phonological Calque & Spelling”, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching” and the coding rules used for content analysis are documented. The four layers – formal, memetic, social and linguistic - of qualitative analysis are described. Finally, the use of the online encyclopedia KnowYourMeme.com is critically discussed and the choice of methods is justified.

The Results chapter presents the findings of the multimodal discourse analysis performed on specimens of each type. The results of the analysis of the “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching” meme types are emphasized, as they are most pertinent to the research interest. The analysis of the “Loan Words” and “Phonological Calque & Spelling” types is combined. The visual distortions present in many memes in the corpus are framed as a discrete communicative mode and the preservation and propagation of old-timey Swiss expressions in memes is highlighted.

The Discussion chapter answers the research questions and focuses on how the meme types “Code Switching” and “Literal Translation” most strongly demonstrate the influence of meme culture on Swiss-German use in the corpus. The ironic use of Swiss-German in the “Schwiizerdütsch” type of memes is discussed, as well as the ironic use of typically Swiss expressions and words. The influence of hiphop culture and AAVE is highlighted again. Concludingly, the literary quality of Swiss-German writing in “Code Switching” and “Literal Translation” memes is emphasized and linked to a discussion of memes as “serious culture” by Nowotny & Reidy. The limitations of my research are described and recommendations for further research on cultural appropria-

tion and power dynamics, language use in other media and the visual rhetoric of Swissness in memes are made.

In the Conclusion, the primary research question is restated and succinctly answered. I reflect on internet memes, the writing process and the importance of precise research questions.

The Appendix contains technical documentations of 4CAT, a software that was used for data collection from Instagram. I hope this and the documentation of other tools and workflows will help other researchers when dealing with the problem of data collection from Instagram. The Appendix also contains the full list of Swiss Instagram meme accounts that I used as a basis for compiling the corpus.

2. Literature Review

There is some research on internet memes *by* Swiss researchers, but there is barely any research *on* Swiss meme culture. In this Literature Review, I will cover the research I was able to find and explain in more detail the research gap addressed by my thesis.

The Literature Review also covers an ongoing discussion on the treatment of memes as folklore and will provide a second key contextual framing for this thesis. In the Introduction, I have made connections to written Swiss-German in advertising and public relations. In this chapter, I will review Swiss-German writing in literary texts and how these practices relate to how Swiss-German is used in internet meme culture.

2.1 State of Research on Swiss Meme Culture

As for research on Swiss memes, I have found a paper discussing the use of memes by Operation Libero¹ (Morger, 2021) and a thesis on the use of memes in Swiss political discourse in general (Morger, 2017). Morger's research is based on current meme studies and is one of the few scientific accounts actually focusing on Swiss-German memes. Please note that the following criticisms are not directed at Morger's research but at the curious display of memetic illiteracy (Knobel & Lankshear, 2007) evident in some of the memes posted by Operation Libero.

Some of the memes that were adapted by Operation Libero and discussed by Morger were oddly outdated and out of touch with meme culture at large. A picture of a frog with text set in the Impact typeface does not necessarily make a meme (Figure 11). In its misappropriation of meme conventions, it calls to mind some of the "shitposts"² discussed later in this thesis. Another meme used by Operation Libero (Figure 12) is an instance of the widespread "Change my mind" meme ('Steven Crowder's "Change My Mind" Campus Sign', 2018). This is another curious use of meme conventions. The man seen sitting at the table is Steven Crowder, a far-right American YouTuber and podcast host. His racist and homophobic behavior is well documented ('Steven Crowder', 2024), so picturing him as campaigning for human dignity ("Menschenwürde gilt für alle" translates to "human dignity applies for everyone") is at the very least naive.

More in tune with meme culture than Operation Libero is a post on the blog of the Bern based Museum of Communication. In "Zur Geschichte des Schweizer Internet Memes"³ (2022), "Stewia" traces the history of Swiss meme culture back to the forums, chat

¹ "Operation Libero defines itself as a liberal transpartisan political movement" ('Operation Libero', 2024).

² Shitposts are a genre of memes that are unfunny or unrelatable on purpose. They are discussed in the Theoretical Framework.

³ "On the history of the Swiss internet meme".

**DIE „SELBSTBESTIMMUNGS-
INITIATIVE“ NIMMT DIE
EUROP. MENSCHENRECHTS-
KONVENTION INS VISIER.**

**DENN SIE WILL DIESE IM ZWEIFEL KÜNDIGEN
UND GEFÄHRDET DAMIT DEN SCHUTZ VOR
STAATLICHER WILLKÜR.**

Figure 11)
“Frog” meme used by
Operation Libero,
from Morger, 2021

Figure 12)
“Change my mind” meme
by Operation Libero,
from Morger, 2021

rooms and event picture websites of the early 2000s. While the post covers many aspects of Swiss meme culture that have not been covered elsewhere, it is a subjective account, written by a prominent member¹ to the Swiss Instagram meme subculture covered in this thesis. Memes by Stewia are also included in the corpus and I will discuss an instance in Results.

Stewia's blog post is from 2022, a year during which memes received a lot of media attention in Switzerland. This is mainly due to the publication of "Memes - Formen und Folgen eines Internetphänomens"² by Joanna Nowotny and Julian Reidy. The monograph by the two Swiss researchers is the first thorough scientific exploration of the phenomenon of internet memes in German³. The discussions on folklore, the fundamental logics of memetic media and considering memes as literary texts is based on or inspired by their work.

Both authors hold PhDs in literature studies and approach the subject of memes from this viewpoint. The book offers a precise analysis of many aspects of internet memes and an up-to-date overview of meme studies and terminology. Despite both authors being based in Bern, a hotspot for parts of the Instagram-based subculture of meme creators, Swiss memes are mentioned only on a couple of pages (Nowotny & Reidy, 2022, p. 77–79). This has informed my decision to focus empirically on a corpus of specifically Swiss image memes.

I have mentioned the attention memes have received in Switzerland after the release of Nowotny & Reidy (2022). Having closely followed Swiss journalistic coverage of the book and memes in general, I found it to be mostly superficial and preoccupied with outdated or sensational aspects of meme culture. Covering the political meaning and influence of memes was very popular. For a while, many Swiss journalists felt a calling to once again relay the tale of Pepe the Frog, the innocent comic character that ended up on the hate symbols list of the American Anti-Defamation League (e.g. 'Comic-Figur Pepe the Frog - Rassisten machten den Frosch zum Troll darum musste er sterben', 2017; Hüsser, 2022; *Netzpolitik*, 2017; *Von Heiterkeit bis Hass*, 2022).

The supposed political influence of memes has not only been covered by journalists; entire books have been written on just this facet of meme culture. Memes and politics have been extensively covered in Donovan et al. (2022), Beran (2019) or the controversial Nagle (2017). Furthermore, meme studies monographs, e.g., Shifman (2013b) and Nowotny & Reidy (2022), usually include a chapter dedicated to political memes and memes as political participation.

The review of existing scholarly and journalistic writing on memes by Swiss researchers and journalists was crucial in identifying a research gap to address. Since there is barely any research on Swiss memes, my thesis addresses this gap by focusing on a) a corpus of memes created by an active subculture of meme creators on Instagram, b) the use of Swiss-German in the corpus, and c) the impact of multimodality on language use.

¹ Disclosure: Stewia is a personal friend of the author.

² "Memes – shapes and consequences of an internet phenomenon".

³ Preceded by an anthology (Bülow et al., 2019) and a non-scientific booklet (Gehlen, 2020).

2.2 Obscene, in Fact: Internet Memes as Folklore

I have argued for the relevance of my research by positioning internet memes as folklore. In this position, I have followed Phillips & Milner (2017) and Shifman (2013b). “Internet memes”, so Shifman (2013b), “can be treated as (post)modern folklore, in which shared norms and values are constructed through cultural artifacts such as Photoshopped images or urban legends”. Nowotny & Reidy (2022) criticize this framing.

Nowotny & Reidy (2022) dedicate a chapter (p. 174-182) to framing memes as folklore, which I will paraphrase and translate hereafter. They question Milner’s and Phillips’ treatment of the “folkloric lens” as “a natural fit for internet memes” (2022, p. 176). While memes can be *compared to* folkloristic production, it does not follow that they *are* folklore (p. 176). According to Nowotny & Reidy (2022), memes allow for a bigger distance to “tradition” and more contextual autonomy, while folklore remains situated in a local context. What memes and folklore do share in common is the interplay of the “new” and the “existing”, of dynamism and conservation (p. 176). Milner (2016) has repeatedly referred to this dynamic as the balance of “fixity and novelty”. In the following, I will shortly touch on the aspect of vulgarity in folklore and then highlight examples from the corpus that directly reference Swiss oral folklore.

A common characteristic of memes and folklore is vulgarity. Phillips & Milner (2017) quote Toelken (1996), who “[...] estimates that the vast majority of orally transmitted folkloric material – up to 80 percent, he suggests – would in fact be considered obscene if encountered out of context.” This rings true for Swiss memes, as will be shown in the later analysis, and is visible in the examples on display throughout this thesis.

Multiple examples of memes that directly referenced Swiss oral folklore were identified in the corpus. In Swiss culture, *Schnupfsprüche* are a form of orally transmitted folklore bearing resemblance to memetic practices. *Schnupfsprüche* are short rhymes that are recited before saying *priis* (a kind of toast akin to “cheers!”) and sharing a round of snuff (‘Schnupftabak’, 2023). They are often vulgar and sometimes downright racist or sexist in nature (‘Schnupfsprüche’, 2023). Figure 13 features a written Schnupfspruch that was placed on top of an oversaturated photograph of a woman imbibing snuff. The text says “LIEBER EN BUUR WO DUET BSCHÖTTE, ALS EN MINARETT VOR DE HÖTTE. PRIIS” and translates to “A farmer who waters plants is preferable to a minaret in front of the house. Cheers!”. The stance of the meme is clearly ironic, mocking the xenophobic nature of the Schnupfspruch. An ironic distance to the content of the meme is further signified by the excessive saturation added. Figure 14 is another instance of the tradition being mocked in a meme. The top text deals with the expectation to come up with a *Schnupfspruch* (about “Sex u Usländer”, “sex and foreigners”) and cites an inane rhyme (“Lieber e bagger im arsch aus es toaster poster”, which I have to translate as “An excavator up one’s ass is preferable to a poster of a toaster”).

Swiss folkloristic traditions such as *Schnupfsprüche* can indeed be seen as relatives and oral ancestors of internet memes, and as Figures 13 and 14 showed, these forms even become subject to

Figure 13)
 "Schnupfspruch" shitpost,
 @mondhausi,
 8 August 2020

"Himmuheiland tammisiech! d Jungs vom Hornusserclub Jassbach wöi eine mit mir schnupfe und erwarte jetzt e arschgeile Schnupfspruch über Sex u Usländer vo mir. Ruhig blibe Tinu du chasch das. Wie isch de nomal gange? Lieber e bagger im arsch aus es toaster poster oder soeppis? ja glaubes de isches de tönt ämu geil ! allez! "

Figure 14)
 "Schnupfspruch" meme,
 @lauericheib69,
 4 November 2020

memesis. As these examples demonstrate and as Nowotny & Reidy (2022) state, the relatedness of internet memes to folkloric forms of expression cannot be denied, but that does not make memes folklore. With the criticisms of the “folkloric lense” by Nowotny & Reidy (2022) in mind, Swiss-German internet memes are positioned in this thesis as sometimes vulgar forms of “populist expression” (Phillips & Milner, 2017) bearing many similarities to (and sometimes referencing) more conventional forms of folklore. For further consideration of the topic, refer to de Seta (2020).

In the next, concluding chapter of this Literature Review, I will show how the influence of African American oral and musical traditions, namely rock and roll and blues music, is traceable in Swiss-German literary writing. Three literary texts will be reviewed, and parallels to influences and language use in meme culture will be established.

2.3 Mundart-Mutations in Contemporary Swiss Literature

A strong American influence and playful mixing of languages are not only evident in memes but can also be observed in literary texts. While literature is widely seen as *Hochkultur*, serious, “high culture”, memes are often dismissed as trivial pop culture. Nowotny & Reidy (2022) elevate the status of memes, by discussing memesis as a *Kulturtechnik*, a cultural technique, applied in the literary text Setz & Klammer (2018). In this section, I will establish further connections between literary texts and internet memes by focusing on word play, language mixing, and the American and African-American influences evident in both forms.

To contextualize language use in memes within literary writing, I will discuss the novel “Blutbuch” by Kim de l’Horizon (2022) and the novellas “acht schtumpfo züri empfernt” by Dominic Oppliger (2018) and “ter fögi ische souhung” by Martin Frank (2023)¹. De l’Horizon’s and Frank’s books were widely discussed, not just because they are rare examples of queer Swiss literature. The discussions also surrounded the radical and innovative use of language. In the following, I will first discuss Frank’s book and how some of the language used and cultural influences map onto today’s Swiss-German meme culture.

Whereas Swiss-German meme culture is influenced by hip-hop culture and African American slang, the subcultural lingo of Frank’s 1979 book is rooted in rock culture. Terms such as “freaks”, “groupies”, “joints” and “rocking and rolling” and bands such as The Rolling Stones and The Who feature repeatedly in “ter fögi ische souhung”. Consider the following sentence.

*im ghörti ganzi alag upferschtercher uaues uwender fögi schpiu
zi gäng au totau wägg uio wöu pminks sone wiude saund hei wie
tschtouns oder thu oder so.*² (Frank, 2023, p. 9)

In Frank’s text, the English “sound” is phonologically spelled in Swiss-German as “saund”, mimicking the pronunciation of the word. The Rolling Stones are translated as “tschtouns” (the

¹ “ter fögi ische souhung” was originally published in 1979. The title roughly translates to “Fögi is a bastard”. “Fögi” is the name of one of the main characters.

² Translation: “He owns the PA system, the amplifiers and everything. And when Fögi plays, everyone is blown away. So am I, because “The Minks” have such a wild sound, like The Rolling Stones or The Who.”

stones) and The Who as “thu”. In other parts of the book, “Freaks” are spelled “friiks”, a marijuana cigarette becomes a “tschoint”. “Rocking” and “rocking and rolling” are translated as “roke” and “rouen uroke”. As I document in the Results chapter, such phonological spellings of terms borrowed from English are prevalent in Swiss meme culture.

The above-mentioned slang terms are signifiers of the slang of the baby boomer generation and the popular music of the time¹. White rock bands such as The Who and The Rolling Stones were interpreting or rather appropriating African-American culture and musical traditions, particularly the blues² and rock and roll. With the popularization of these musical traditions, slang terms rooted African American English such as “cool” (Skinner, 2014), “joint” and “rock and roll” were adopted and spread around the world. Just as in today's meme culture, an African American influence can be identified in Franks text from 1979.

In meme culture, Frank's baby boomer cohort and their attitudes often bear the brunt of many memetic jokes. See Figure 15 for an example, a highly ironic, and visually distorted post by Swiss-German meme account @draindler.page, which sounds like it could have been written by somebody who lived through 70s rock culture. The text translates to “Back in my day, we used to smoke, drink, fuck, and listen to The Rolling Stones. All kids care about these days is the weather in 100 years. Such fools!”

Frank has found a unique way of writing in the Swiss-German dialect that was considered radical at the time of the release of his book. The writing can be hard to decipher and is wildly inventive. Such literary playfulness (and obscurantism) is present in many Swiss-German memes. To demonstrate this, we can look at the title of Frank's book, “ter fögi ische souhung”. “Souhung” is an expletive, literally meaning “pig dog”. “Hung” is “dog” in Bernese dialect and is a term often used in Swiss-German memes, either literally or as a translation of the African American slang term “dog” or “dawg”, meaning friend or buddy. See Figure 16 for an example of how African-American English terms such as “homies” and arguably “hound”, are used in a Swiss-German meme.

Are there parallels to language use in meme culture in more recent literature? Oppliger (2018) is intertextually referencing Frank (2023) by using a quote from his book as a disclaimer on the first page of his dialect novella. The novella was published as part of “edition spoken script”, a series of texts originally intended for spoken word and poetry readings. This back and forth between spoken and written language is typical of Swiss meme culture. Oppliger's text is less situated in a subcultural context than Frank's. English loan words are used in the text, as they are in everyday spoken Swiss-German. For example, Oppliger is phonologically spelling widespread loan words such as “e-mail”, “jeans” and “teenies” as “iimeyl”, “tschiins” and “tiinis”, the Swiss-German imitating the pronunciation of the English words. The quote below translates to “And the other guy probably has better things to do than writing emails to those in the perfect world.”

*unte ander häpwaschinli ä gschiders ztue als denenide heile wält
es iimeyl z schriibe (Oppliger, 2018, p. 56)*

¹ Now sometimes ironically referred to as “dad rock”.

² Funnily, Paul McCartney of The Beatles has referred to The Rolling Stones as a “blues cover band” (Remnick, 2021).

Figure 15)
"Stones" shitpost,
@draindler.page,
3 April 2020

Figure 16)
"Hound" meme,
@jesus.nr1,
6 March 2020

Translations that mimic the pronunciation of English words can be found both in literary texts and meme culture. In Swiss meme culture, such translations are often a source of humour, while in Frank's and Oppliger's texts, they reflect subcultural belonging and how some Swiss people actually speak.

I will conclude this discussion of Swiss-German literary texts and their parallels to linguistic playfulness and language mixing in meme culture by considering Kim de L'Horizon's "Blutbuch" (De l'Horizon, 2022). The novel was published in 2022 and won the German book price the same year. The book is multilingual, just as the Swisscom advertisement discussed in the Introduction and many Swiss-German memes. For the most part, it is written in *Hochdeutsch*, with interspersed diary entries written in a simpler and distinctly Swiss style of German. The final chapter of the book is written entirely in English. De l'Horizon switches languages freely throughout, for example, in the following sentences, which translate to "Especially about copper beeches. Rich kids were, once again, to blame. Distinction distinction, we are more fancy than you."

Ganz besonders um Blutbuchen. Schuld dran waren wieder mal die rich kids, distinction distinction, wir sind fancyer als ihr. (De l'Horizon, 2022, p. 135)

De l'Horizon (2022) echoes the widespread use of anglicisms and language switching prevalent in everyday Swiss-German. Post-modern texts such as memes and De l'Horizon's novel often feature a meta layer, where the texts themselves become a matter of discussion or reference. The protagonist of "Blutbuch" is writing about their conflicted relationship with Swiss-German in the concluding, English chapter of the book:

And still - writing in High-German, writing in English means I am betraying Mum and you, means I change class, I refuse the language of my ancestors, I refuse the farmer language that does not have fixed grammar rules, that exists only in spoken form. (De l'Horizon, 2022)

The juxtaposition of Swiss-German, perceived as a "farmer language" and English, specifically African American English, perceived as "cool", is a widespread practice in Swiss-German meme culture.

As I have demonstrated, Swiss-German internet memes can be situated in a wider context of literary writing and the professional world of advertising. Together with text messages, social media commentary, advertising, and "spoken scripts", memes are testament to Swiss-German no longer existing "only in spoken form" (De l'Horizon, 2022).

In this Literature Review, I have addressed the research gap on Swiss meme culture, tracked a discussion on the treatment of memes as folklore, and compared language use in Swiss memes and literary writing. In the next chapter, I will explain the Theoretical Framework underpinning my research. Phenomena such as borrowing words from other languages, multimodal communication, and the concept of internet memes in general will be elaborated on in detail.

3. Theoretical Framework

The Theoretical Framework for my thesis is grounded in the field of meme studies and work by scholars such as Shifman, Milner, and Reidy/Nowotny. Linguistic concepts are used to describe phenomena such as borrowing, calquing, and code switching. In this chapter, I will define and explain these key terms and concepts. The chapter is structured along the analytical framework detailed in Research Design and Methodology and covers the memetic, formal, social, and linguistic aspects that are the focus of this thesis. I will start with the question of what a meme is and current approaches to defining this notoriously slippery concept, which pioneering meme scholar Limor Shifman has described as a “conceptual troublemaker” (Shifman, 2013a).

3.1 Memetic Layer

3.1.1 Memes, Memetics, Memesis: Fundamental Logics

The discussion of what a meme is has to start with the inevitable “Dawkins part” of every discussion of internet memes.

The term meme goes back to British evolutionary biologist Richard Dawkins (Dawkins, 2016), who coined it in his 1976 book “The Selfish Gene”. Dawkins’ aim was to describe human culture from the perspective of evolutionary biology. Memes in Dawkins’ original definition were “units of cultural transmission”. These units were described by Dawkins as propagating “themselves in the meme pool by leaping from brain to brain via a process which, in the broad sense, can be called imitation” (2016, p. 192). Obviously predating the world wide web, invented in 1989 (“The Birth of the Web”, 2024), Dawkins’ meme was not intended to describe internet memes. In 1993, Mike Godwin started using the term “internet meme” to describe content spreading via the message boards, Usenet groups, and email lists of the early internet (“Internet Meme”, 2023). In true memetic fashion, the term caught on and started spreading virally before becoming the focus of academic research.

Early scholarly work on internet memes built directly on the Dawkinsian conception, for example, the often-cited Knobel & Lankshear (2007) article¹. I will not go into much further detail on the history of the term and Dawkinsian memetics since it has been discussed extensively by meme scholars, for example by Milner (2016) or more recently by Schlaile (2021). Shifman (2013b) discusses the history of the term in a chapter of her essential monograph. For the rest of this thesis, I will use the terms “internet meme” and “meme” interchangeably and will use “memetic” in the sense of “pertaining to internet memes”, not as a reference to Dawkinsian memetics.

¹ Research on internet memes grounded in Dawkinsian memetics with no references to Milner, Shifman, et al. is rare these days but still exists; see, for example, Valensise et al. (2021).

The conceptual framing of internet memes in this thesis builds on work by Shifman (2013b), Milner (2016) and Nowotny & Reidy (2022). It is with Shifman's definition (2013b, p. 41) in mind that I use the term meme or internet meme. Shifman defined the internet meme not as a single artifact but as a "(a) group of digital items sharing common characteristics of content, form, and/or stance, which (b) were created with awareness of each other, and (c) were circulated, imitated, and/or transformed via the Internet by many users." According to Nissenbaum & Shifman (2017) a meme is a textual group, and a particular "member" of a group is a meme instance. Shifman's definition is still current and widely used, for example in a recent paper by Rogers & Giorgi (2023). Nowotny & Reidy (2022) have criticized it for not emphasizing referentiality enough.

Shifman's definition was extended by Milner (2016), who has defined "five fundamental logics evident in the creation, circulation, and transformation of memetic media: multimodality, reappropriation, resonance, collectivism, and spread" (p. 16). For describing the intertwined processes of circulation, imitation, and transformation essential to memes, Nowotny & Reidy (2022) have coined the term "memesis" (p. 16). Memesis is intended to describe memetic transformation and circulation more precisely than simple imitation does and further extends Shifman's definition, with a stronger focus on referentiality.

Memes are very diverse and heterogeneous artifacts and take on many forms and stances. In the next section, I will draw a tentative distinction between memes and shitposts, a memetic genre rife with obscenity, nonsensical humor, and grotesque aesthetics.

3.1.2 Cheggt Niemer u Närvt Aui: Memes vs. Shitposts

In this thesis and pertaining to the image-based memes at hand, shitposts are treated as a genre of memes. Shitposting can be described as ironically posting content that is unfunny or incomprehensible in order "to mock, insult or amuse" (thesinner6666, 2018). This content can come in different media, such as text, memes, digital images, or videos. The definition of shitposting is constantly shifting (Cavanaugh, 2021, p. 1). Whether shitposting is a style or genre of memes, an aesthetic, or a category entirely separate from memes is debatable. Memes and shitposts, I argue, can be positioned at opposite ends of a continuum of stances. Figure 17 illustrates this tentative distinction and includes aesthetics, because the focus of my research is on image-based shitposts and memes.

Shitposts take an adversarial, discordant stance, and in the case of image-based posts, they often use "grotesque" aesthetics and frequently obscure and unrelatable references. The purpose of a shitpost is not to maximize relatability and spread; instead, shitposts appeal to a smaller collective of insiders. In a post by @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck on Instagram¹, the general stance of shitposting is succinctly described as "cheggt niemer u närvt aui": nobody will get this and it will annoy everyone.

Memes, I argue, may also contain inside jokes and obscure references, but in general aim for relatability. Their aesthetics are less distorted, and the references used are generally more popular and

¹ The shitpost containing the phrase is the focus of my analysis of memes of the Code Switching type in Results.

The Shitpost-Meme Continuum

Figure 17)
Shitpost-Meme Continuum,
by author, February 2024

transparent. The aim of memes, I argue, is to be relatable to and decodable (Hall et al., 2003) by a larger audience and not just a small group of insiders.

Throughout this thesis, I distinguish between memes and shitposts and will denote specimens as such, bearing in mind that both genres exist on a continuum and that not every instance can be conclusively classified.

In the genre of image-based shitposting, the result of the combination of multiple communication modes is often the opposite of “eye candy”. In the following section, I will explain how this peculiar aesthetic has been described by scholars and artists.

3.2 Formal Layer

3.2.1 Poor, Fried Images: Memetic Aesthetics

Many image-based memes and a considerable portion of the specimens in the corpus are far removed from conventional and professional standards of visual beauty, such as those prevalent on Instagram and in advertising and public relations. This peculiar aesthetic has been described as “shitpics” (Feldman, 2014) and “internet ugly” (Douglas, 2014). Galip (2021), building on these themes, has described the output of a niche group of Instagram meme accounts as “grotesque” and “carnavalesque”. Steyerl (2009) has famously defended the aesthetic and artfully described such “poor images” as follows.

The poor image is a rag or a rip; an AVI or a JPEG, a lumpen proletarian in the class society of appearances, ranked and valued according to its resolution. The poor image has been uploaded, downloaded, shared, reformatted, and reedited. (Steyerl, 2009)

In meme culture, these processes of degradation are often an intended, deliberate part of the appeal and serve a communicative purpose. They are a meta layer, where the focus is not so much on the content of a meme but instead on aesthetic deviation. Figure 18 is an example of a conventional meme with clear aesthetics, while Figure 19 is an example of a shitpost with grotesque aesthetics and a discordant, unrelatable stance.

In 2020 and 2021, so-called “deep-fried” memes were popular in Swiss meme culture. The memes on display throughout this thesis contain many examples of heavily degraded and distorted memes. Deep-frying “involves the degradation of visual quality and linguistic comprehensibility for the purposes of humor”, so Kowalchuk (2020). Kowalchuk (2020) has identified “saturated coloration; increased grain; lowered resolution or increased compression; warping or bubbling effects; unnecessary lens flaring; excessive emoji usage; and linguistic misdirection or formulaic subversion” as formal qualities of deep-fried memes. The style and its history are also described in ‘Deep Fried Memes’ (2017).

Swiss German is often used for “linguistic misdirection” and “formulaic subversion” in Swiss memes, as some of the memes on display in this thesis demonstrate. Furthermore, due to the popularity of the deep-fried style at the time, distortion was applied to many memes in the corpus. In my analysis and the *Results* chapter, I will treat visible and excessive distortion, filtering, or saturation as a distinct mode of communication.

Figure 18)
 "KV/Bauarbeiter" meme,
 @swissmeme, 4 April 2020

Figure 19)
 "Erich Hess" shitpost,
 @chline_hutzu,
 1 February 2021

3.2.2 Multimodality, Modes and Media

According to Milner (2016), “multimodality—in its intense integration of word, image, audio, video, and hypertext—facilitates the vibrant creative expression and conversation at the heart of memetic media” (p. 218). In Milner’s discussion of the concept, he also distinguishes between *media* and *modes*.

There’s a difference, argues Carey Jewitt (2004), between communication media and communicative modes. Media are “technologies of dissemination,” such as newspapers, radio, film, television, or the internet. Modes are “technologies of representation,” such as written language, image, audio, video, and hypertext. (2006, p. 177).

The distinction between media and mode is fluid. Kress & Van Leeuwen (2001) argue that “...media become modes once their principles of semiosis begin to be conceived of in more abstract ways (as ‘grammars’ of some kind). This in turn will make it possible to realize them in a range of media. They lose their tie to a specific form of material realization.” For memes, this means that they can become a mode of communication, for example, in a forum discussion or in instant messaging. Furthermore, the characters, catchphrases, and conventions of memes can be understood as a kind of grammar, as abstract underlying structures and ideas, which allow for their realization in different media.

Kress & Van Leeuwen (2001) mention literary novels and academic treatises as examples of monomodal media, which were often “dense pages of print” entirely devoid of other communication modes such as illustrations. In contrast, multimodality is defined as “... the use of several semiotic modes in the design of a semiotic product or event, together with the particular way in which these modes are combined” (2001, p. 20).

Concluding the foregoing discussion, memes are treated as *media* in this thesis. Communication *modes* are combined in these media, and it is from their combination and hierarchical order that we have to make sense of their communicative purpose.

Socially, memes are a way to comment on and to frame the *Welt-geschehen*, world affairs and historic events. The primary focus of my research interest is the analysis of formal and linguistic aspects of memes, but Knobel & Lankshear (2007, p.219) stressed that the social significance of memes has to be considered when dealing with them. In this spirit, the “memetic shadowing” of events will be elaborated on in the next section.

3.3 Social Layer

3.3.1 Memetic Shadow: If an Event is not memed, did it even happen?

Journalistic coverage of historic events is one of many potential sources of memetic discourse. Almost anything can be turned into a meme or become cultural source material for memes. If it exists, there is probably a meme of it. Indeed, there seems to be an increasing number of people who consume news by way of internet memes and social media, eschewing traditional journalistic media. Arguably, sloganesque news headlines, such as those by the *Blick* tabloid discussed in the Introduction, are inherently memeable. In

an article on srf.ch ('So gehen wir mit Kriegs-News um das sagt die Medienpsychologin', 2022), anonymous user "Userin TPA" has the following to say about their consumption of news, notably in Swiss-German:

Luege set Johre ke Nachrechte meh. Be deför uf Reddit. Öpper macht halt Memes öber momentäni Situatione. Wenns die interessiert chasch emmer no go noche läse.

The article is concerned with how the srf.ch community is coping with news of war and other current events. Translating the above statement from dialect to English, "Userin TPA" is saying that they "have not watched any news in years. Instead, I'm on Reddit. Someone will make memes about current events. If you're really interested, you can go look it up."

This filtering and contextualizing function of memes has aptly been described by Hondroudakis (2021) as a "memetic shadow".

Essentially, the memetic ecology at large serves to mediate the enormous flows of information and affect, enacting a sorting, matching, and grammatizing process on public affairs. Every major event, development, or process [...] is refigured by a memetic shadow – which in turn serves to identify politico-aesthetic lines of division and commonality, particularity and universality. (p. 188)

In the social layer of the analysis, I will highlight the social significance and the memetic shadowing of world affairs. A critical discussion of the phenomenon of the consumption of news by way of memes is worthy of further research but goes beyond the scope of this thesis.

In the next section, I will explain the key linguistic concepts and terminology underlying the analysis of language use in Swiss-German memes.

3.4 Linguistic Layer

How is Swiss-German used in image memes posted on Instagram? In order to answer this question, linguistic concepts are deployed, especially pertaining to the borrowing and translating of expressions and words from other languages.

The term "vernacular" is used throughout this thesis. Both African-American English and Swiss-German are vernaculars, "native to a given community, as opposed to a learned or other second language" (Matthews, 2014, p. 428). Vernaculars are languages that are "not standardized, of non-standard varieties of those that are, of forms used locally or characteristic of non-dominant groups or classes" (p. 428). On a related note, the term "colloquial" is "applied to vocabulary and grammar typical of informal speech and not normally used in formal speech and writing" (Brown & Miller, 2013, p. 86).

3.4.1 No official Rules: Swiss-German and Hochdeutsch

Swiss-German is an umbrella term for the many dialects spoken in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. It is distinguished from Swiss Standard German or "high German", *Hochdeutsch*. *Hochdeutsch* denotes the German spoken and written in Germany, while Swiss Standard German is a Swiss variant of "Standard Ger-

man” (‘Swiss-German’, 2024). In Switzerland, “... all formal writing, newspapers, books and much informal writing is done in Swiss Standard German [...]” (‘Swiss-German’, 2024). Furthermore, “Swiss Standard German is fully understandable to all speakers of Standard German, while many people in Germany – especially in the north – do not understand Swiss-German” (‘Swiss-German’, 2024). When it comes to Swiss-German use in memes, it is important to note that “there are no official rules of Swiss-German orthography” (‘Swiss-German’, 2024). This is exemplified by Wikipedia listing five different spellings of Swiss-German – I have opted for “Schwiizerdütsch” to name a type of memes I have identified in my research.

A 2013 census revealed that Swiss-German was spoken by 63,5 % of the population (4.93 million people), making it the most used of the four official languages spoken in Switzerland. The official languages are Swiss Standard German, French, Italian, and Rhaeto-Romanic. Loan words and calques from French and Italian are common in Swiss-German.

For the purpose of this thesis, it is sufficient to have a basic understanding of the distinction between Hochdeutsch and Swiss-German and the fact that there are no fixed rules for spelling and orthography. When I use Swiss-German in this thesis, I mean the “unruly” dialects and not the formal *Hochdeutsch*.

3.4.2 Everything but the Burden¹: African-American Vernacular English in Swiss Meme Culture

Jackson (2016) states that “we know that internet culture depends on Black people” and furthermore, “Black language itself works as a sort of metastasized meme, seized by non-Black entities and replicated (not so clumsily, anymore) to gain access to a kind of mass appealing Cool”. In the analysed corpus, I have found many instances of “Black language” being borrowed and calqued in Swiss-German memes, confirming Jackson’s notion.

But what exactly is this “Black language”? African-American Vernacular English (AAVE) is a “variety of English identified as that of urban communities especially in the USA whose members are historically of African descent” (Matthews, 2014). Just as Swiss-German is a variety of standard German, AAVE is a variety of standard English with “its own unique grammatical, vocabulary, and accent features” (‘African-American Vernacular English’, 2024). AAVE is also referred to as Ebonics (Rickford, 2012) or Black English (Manuel Arturo, 2015).

More precisely, Manuel Arturo (2015) refers to an “imagined Black English” which he describes as “the phenomenon of non-black English speakers with no fluency using real or imaginary linguistic features of Black English”. The use of expressions and words borrowed and translated from AAVE in Swiss-German meme culture aptly fits this description.

I will refer to Black English, or Ebonics, as AAVE for the rest of this thesis, taking the following important points into consideration:

¹ “Everything but the burden” is the title of a poem by Florence Tate and was used by Greg Tate as the title of the collection of essays on “what white people are taking from Black culture” (Tate, 2003).

- AAVE is not “slang” or a “lesser” form of standard English (‘A Brief History of AAVE’, 2021), it is a “a fully-formed linguistic system, as all dialects and languages are” (Manuel Arturo, 2015)
- Not all African-Americans speak AAVE, and not all AAVE speakers are African-American (Baron, Dennis, 2005)
- “AAVE is just as sophisticated as standard English and deploys many distinctions and nuances standard English lacks” (‘A Brief History of AAVE’, 2021)

AAVE is sometimes conflated with “Internet English”, arguably constituting a form of “whitewashing” and appropriation (Chery, 2022; ‘White Gen Z Has Suddenly “Discovered” AAVE. Now They’re Trying to Claim It’, 2022). “Internet English” is depending on the creativity and cultural capital of AAVE, but but they are not the same. An example of such conflation is the article on the AAVE term “thicc” on KnowYourMeme.com. It is positioned as “part of a series on Internet Slang” (‘Thicc’, 2016).

Just as memes have been repeatedly called the “lingua franca” of the internet, AAVE “is becoming America’s youth lingua franca, especially since the mainstreaming of hip-hop” (Henderson, 2009). Manuel Arturo (2015) states that “the advent of hip-hop and the internet have arguably spread Black media farther than ever before”. Tate (2003) has explained the appeal of hip-hop presciently (and implicitly, memes as a prosperous form of culture in the digital age) as follows:

The aura and global appeal of hip-hop lie in both its perceived Blackness (hip, stylish, youthful, alienated, rebellious, sensual) [...]. The way hip-hop collapsed art, commerce, and interactive technology into one mutant animal from its inception seems to have almost predicted the forms culture would have to take to prosper in the digital age. (2003, p. 7)

The topics of racial stereotyping, cultural appropriation, and blackface are acknowledged and discussed by meme studies scholars and internet linguists. Nissenbaum & Shifman (2018) state that “social identity representation in global memetic culture is therefore one of standardization and orthodoxy, favoring stereotypical representations of marginalized groups while portraying ethnically dominant males as the standard bearers.” A specific example of stereotyping, the “Successful Black Man” meme template, was discussed by Shifman (2013b) and Milner (2016). The website-based “Black People Love Us!” meme was discussed in Knobel & Lankshear (2007).

McCulloch (2019) traces the origins of “internet slang” such as “af” (“as fuck”), “on fleek” and “bae” to Hispanic and African-American roots and highlights how African American cultural forms have been influential long before the invention of the internet.

Terms associated with African American music, including blues, jazz, rock and roll, and rap, have all made their way into broader Western culture, while the speakers who originated them continue to be stigmatized for the way they talk. (McCulloch, 2019).

The influence of blues, jazz, rock and roll terms was evident in the Swiss-German writing of Frank (2023) and the influence of rap slang is evident in contemporary Swiss meme culture.

3.4.3 Calque, Translation and Loan Words

This thesis is focused on identifying memetic Swiss-German mutations. To describe these “mutations” more precisely, linguistic vocabulary is helpful. This section will provide an understanding of the linguistic terminology used throughout this thesis. These explanations are mostly based on Matthews, 2014.

In the source corpus, I was able to identify the frequent use of loan words. A loan word is “imported by borrowing from another language” (Matthews, 2014, p. 229). The English “chamber” is given as an example for borrowing the French “chambre” (2014, p. 229). In Swiss-German, “computer”, “ciao” and “merci” are examples of loan words from English, Italian, and French prevalent in everyday language use. A further example is “Folklore”, which has been loaned from English and has become fully integrated into German. In German, there is also the concept of a *Fremdwort* (literally a “foreign word”) to denote words borrowed from antique languages such as Greek or Latin (‘Fremdwort’, 2023). *Fremdwörter* are distinguished from loan words in German.

A majority of the loan words used in the source corpus are borrowed from the English language, often from AAVE. Expressions borrowed from the English language are called anglicisms (‘Anglizismus’, 2023). The phenomenon of anglicisms in German is often criticized by language purists. For a discussion, refer to Dürscheid & Frick (2016).

Just as “folklore” is borrowed, the term “loan word” itself is borrowed. It is actually a translation of the German *Lehnwort*. Such loan translations are referred to as calque. Calque, in turn, is a word borrowed from French. Looking at the meaning of the word calque, an interesting parallel to memesis is revealed: to calque is to imitate or copy (‘Calque’, 2024). Calques differ from loan words in that they are translated into the target language. For example, the German *Wolkenkratzer* is a calque of the English “skyscraper”.

Different types of calques can be found in the corpus analysed in this thesis. There are phraseological calques, which are literal translations of phrases or expressions. For example, the AAVE “be like” is sometimes translated as “sein wie”. Sometimes, “literally” is, ironically, literally mis-translated as *literarisch*, which actually means “literary”.

Phonological calques imitate the pronunciation of words and become integrated in the target language. In Swiss-German, *äxgüsi* is a phonological calque of the French “excusez”. In Thai, the word “siwalai” is believed to be a phonological calque of the English “civilized” (‘The Concept of “Siwalai” Emerged as Western Styles Mingled with Thai’, 2018). For further discussion of loan translation, refer to ‘Loan Words and Calques in The English Language’ (2020) and ‘Calque’ (2024).

What I have tentatively dubbed Swiss-German “mutations” are actually phonological calques, literal translations, loan words, and “plain” Swiss-German. These are four of five types of language use I have identified in the corpus. The fifth type is code switching.

Code switching is the “switching in speech between different languages, dialects etc.” and can occur “within sentences or at sentence boundaries” (Matthews, 2014). In image-based Swiss-Ger-

man memes, codes are often switched from English to Swiss-German, using a combination of communication modes.

Code switching in Swiss-German memes often occurs in the context of a memetic catchphrase. A catchphrase is a “phrase or expression recognized by its repeated utterance” and often humorous in nature (‘Catchphrase’, 2023). Catchphrases can come in the form of so-called snowclones, which are phrasal templates or clichés, in “which certain words may be replaced with another to produce new variations with altered meanings” (‘Snowclone’, 2023). “Fuck X, All My Homies use Y” and “All Your X Are Belong To Us” are prominent examples of memetic snowclones (‘All Your Base Are Belong to Us’, 2008; Fuck X, All My Homies use Y, 2019). When the Xs and Ys are filled in with Swiss-German expressions, this constitutes code switching by way of snowclones.

3.5 Summary of Key Concepts

In summary, the following ideas and concepts form the Theoretical Framework of my thesis.

- Internet memes are groups of highly referential, multimodal, folkloristic digital artifacts
- Shitposts are a memetic genre, distinguished from memes by their purposefully unrelatable stance
- Some memes use a grotesque aesthetic and use visual distortion as a discrete communicative mode
- Multimodality is key to understanding the communicative purpose of and language use in memes
- Memes “shadow” current affairs and historic events and to some people, are a news source
- Swiss-German is a primarily spoken vernacular with no official codified rules
- AAVE and African American cultural forms such as rap music are highly influential on internet culture, and on Swiss-German meme culture
- What I have dubbed Swiss-German “mutations” are actually five types of language use: “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Loan Words”, “Phonological Calque & Spelling”, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching”.

This typology, the associated coding rules and the methods used to develop it will be described in the next chapter.

Overview of research questions, methodology and analytical layers

Figure 20] Thesis methodology overview, by author, February 2024

4. Research Design and Methodology

In this chapter, I will describe how the corpus was compiled and what criteria were defined. A mixed-methods approach was applied to the corpus in the form of image type analysis, which combines quantitative content analysis and qualitative multimodal discourse analysis. In short, you will find anything related to the “how” of my research in this chapter, starting with a description of the corpus and its criteria. Figure 20 provides an overview of the research design.

4.1 Criteria for Meme Source Corpus

I am working with primary sources i.e. static image memes downloaded from Instagram. Over the past three years, I have collected a list of more than 100 Swiss Instagram meme accounts (Appendix B). Accounts from this list were included in the corpus if they fit the following criteria:

- The accounts mostly share memes written in Swiss-German dialect
- The accounts became active on or before March 16, 2021
- The accounts were still active in 2023
- The accounts post mostly original content; they are not compilation accounts

The list of corpus accounts can be found in Appendix C. To judge whether an account fits these criteria, I am noting the date of the first feed post and the date of the latest post.

I chose this period because I have observed an increase in the number of Swiss-German meme accounts during the period of the COVID-related “lockdown” in Switzerland. Switzerland has declared an *ausserordentliche Lage* (an “extraordinary situation” or a state of emergency) and effected a “lockdown” on 16 March 2020 (‘Coronavirus’, 2020). Many of the accounts that were active during this period were and continue to be influential and have inspired other people to start Swiss-German “meme pages”. In regards to the content, I define the following criteria:

- For technical and pragmatic reasons, I only examine image memes that have been shared as posts. Video memes and content shared in stories are omitted.
- The content was posted in the period of March 16, 2020 to March 16, 2021.

From the compiled list of 113 accounts in Appendix B, 34 accounts fit the account criteria (Appendix C). I have downloaded all image posts up to September 7, 2023 for each account. The total number of all the image posts I have downloaded from these 34 accounts is 29505. Of these, 7428 were posted between March 16, 2020 and March 16, 2021. As this number is still too high to be feasibly ana-

lysed during a master's project, I had to further reduce the number. I have done this by working with randomized samples of the overall corpus.

I was able to confirm a central hypothesis underpinning my research: that the number of Swiss meme accounts on Instagram had increased during the pandemic. To verify this assumption, I have evaluated the dates of the first posts for all of the 113 accounts on the list (see Appendix) . The following table lists the results of this evaluation.

Table 1) Date of first post for all accounts in account list.

Date of first post	Number of accounts	Percentage
Before Lockdown	24	21.24%
During Lockdown	47	62.83%
After Lockdown	42	37.17%

The table above showed that only 24 of the 113 accounts in the list were active before March 16, 2020, the start of the COVID “lockdown”. The majority of the accounts became active during (47) or after March 16, 2021, a year after the “extraordinary situation” has been declared by the Swiss government (42).

4.2 Data Collection and Processing

4.2.1 Difficulty in accessing and processing research data

Instagram makes it difficult for researchers to access content shared on the platform. Posts cannot be saved directly to the computer using the browser's save function. So one is forced to take screenshots, which also include the navigation arrows of slide posts. This is extremely time-consuming. Fortunately, I learned about the tools provided by the “Digital Methods Initiative” at the conference “Images in Social Media Research: Digital Tools and Methodological Challenges” in February 2023. Their Instagram scraper “Zeeschuimer” can be used in combination with the 4CAT Capture and Analysis Toolkit (Peeters & Hagen, 2022) to download image files.

4CAT was crucial in being able to collect content from the selected accounts. Without it, a quantitative content analysis I wanted to conduct would not have been possible. However, after having downloaded the needed files, I was confronted with problems with data handling. To be able to work with these files, I had to rename them and then select the files that fit the criteria. To make working with these files more feasible, I have renamed them to be human-readable and processable by scripts. For example, this is the filename of a file downloaded from Instagram.

121318980_3345290882226607_7327990791752254537_n.jpg

Using a Linux shell script I have developed, I have renamed the files to adhere to the following convention:

20201022-104417-chline_hutzu-CGpJVLArio.jpg

The file names now contain the post date (2021022) and time stamp (104417), the account name (chline_hutzu) and the post ID (CGpJVLArio) on Instagram. For each account, I have opened six random image files and the corresponding Instagram posts to ver-

ify that the renaming worked as intended. Verification also highlighted a technical problem I had to be aware of in my analysis of the corpus. I have assumed that video posts are not downloaded at all. However, it turned out that the first frame of a video post is downloaded as an image file. The Instagram post ID makes it possible to look up posts for which it is unclear whether they are an image post or a video post. The scripts developed and technical details are documented in the appendix. I will discuss the methods used to analyze the corpus next.

4.2.2 Quantitative Methods: Content Analysis and Image Type Analysis

The source corpus was examined using image type analysis (Lobinger, 2019), which combines a quantitative and qualitative approach and is based on (visual) content analysis (Rose, 2022). Content analysis is a quantitative method and outlines rigorous rules and procedures for “selecting, coding and quantitative analysis of large numbers of images” (Rose, 2022). According to Rose (2022), it was developed with photographs appearing in mass media in mind. The method also allows for analysis of social media content, photographs posted on Instagram, and even manga comics. With the research questions in mind, I have used content analysis to identify types of images in the corpus based on language use. For the identified types, I will analyze one image representative of the type.

Categories or types are developed based on subsets of five randomly selected memes from each account, amounting to a total of 167 memes. In order to verify and improve the reliability of the developed coding categories, I will test the types with multiple randomized subsets of the corpus. In order to associate the image files directly with categories and codes, the software QualCoder is used.

Content analysis and image type analysis are means to an end. The methods are applied to identify types or broader categories of memes, which can then be analysed qualitatively. The identified types serve to answer RQ2: What types of memetic Swiss-German mutations can be identified? In the following, I will describe the coding rules I have established and followed in my analysis.

4.3 Meme Typology and Coding Rules

The result of content analysis has been the identification of a typology of five meme types based on diverging language use. Further meme types were identified but excluded from analysis. These include image-only memes, which may contain Swiss visual references but no Swiss-German text. Memes with text written exclusively in another language than Swiss-German were excluded, too. For the meme types described in the following, this means that they all include text written in Swiss-German dialect. A closer examination of the corpus also revealed many memes containing audio and video. These were coded as “invalid”, since the focus of this thesis is on image memes.

Meme Type 1: Schwiizerdütsch

Description: “Schwiizerdütsch” memes contain no recognizable loan words or calque.

Schwiizer kaufet am 7ni morgue alles leer und seget denn "de schneller isch de gschwinder 😊"

Figure 21)
"De schneller isch de gschwinder" meme,
@hajdi.ch,
14 March 2020

Figure 22)
"Livestreams" meme,
@stewia2046,
26 February 2020

Figure 23)
"Messätsch" shitpost,
@samanthatic,
May 5 2020

Coding Rule: Memes are categorized as this type if the written text is “purely” Swiss-German.

Example: Figure 21 is written in Swiss-German dialect, and contains no loan words or translations. It translates to “Swiss people will buy up everything at 7 in the morning and then say ”first come, first serve”¹.

Meme Type 2: Loan Words

Description: Memes of this type use loan words from other languages than Swiss-German.

Coding Rule: Memes are typified as “Loan Words” if they use one or more words borrowed from another language than Swiss-German. It differs from the “Code Switching” type, in which expressions and phrases from other languages are mixed with Swiss-German.

Example: Figure 22 contains the English loan words “instant” and “livestreams”. Notably, instead of borrowing “instant noodles”, the dialect *nudle* was used.

Meme Type 3: Phonological Calque & Spelling

Description: These memes contain written imitations of the pronunciation of words from another language.

Coding Rule: Memes contain written forms of the pronunciation of words from other languages.

Example: In the text of Figure 23 the English “message” is phonologically written as “MESSÄTSCH”. Young members of SVP, the far-right *Schweizerische Volkspartei* (“Swiss people’s party”), are addressed with the phonological spelling “ESVAUPELER”.

Meme Type 4: Literal Translation

Description: In this type of meme, sentence structures (syntax) and terms are literally translated to Swiss-German while keeping the original grammatical structure.

Coding Rule: In the text, syntactic or phraseological structures are directly translated to Swiss-German.

Example: In Figure 24, the phrase “Mis gsicht wenn” is a phraseological calque or literal translation of “my face when”, a common catchphrase in memes². Other examples of literal translation in Swiss memes are “be like” translated as *sein wie* or “literally” being (mis-) translated as *literarisch* (meaning “literary”).

¹ A reference to COVID-19 related panic buying. The expression “de schneller isch de gschwinder” is typically Swiss. Literally, it translates to “the faster (person) is the quicker (person)”.

² It is combined with the Swiss expression “de föifer unds Weggli ha” which is similar in meaning to “you can’t have your cake and eat it, too”.

Figure 24)
"Mis gsicht wenn" shitpost,
@drainder.page,
22 January 2021

Figure 25)
"Fiescheralp" meme,
@jesus.nr1,
6 March 2020

Meme Type 5: Code Switching

Description: In this type of meme, languages are switched freely within the same sentence or within the context of the meme.

Coding Rule: Memes of this type contain text wherein Swiss-German is mixed with one or more other languages. The use of one or several loan words does not qualify for this type. Languages have to be structurally mixed, containing expressions and structures from multiple languages.

Example: In Figure 25 the phrase “FUCK Oerlike ALL MY HOMIES si wohnhaft i fiescheralp” is an example of code switching between Swiss-German and English.

Instances of each meme type were analysed qualitatively.

4.4 Qualitative Method: Multimodal Discourse Analysis

For the qualitative analysis of the identified meme types, the framework described by Nowotny & Reidy (2022, pp. 65–68) was used. Reidy and Nowotny use four steps or layers to analyze the multimodal aspects, context, and discourse of memes. Furthermore, the four layers are used to structure the *theoretical framework*. For this thesis and the research questions, I have adapted the framework thusly, allowing for a multimodal discourse analysis.

Layer I: Formal Analysis

The meme and the communication modalities used are described. This corresponds to Panofsky’s first level of visual interpretation, the “primary” or “pre-iconographic” analysis (Rose, 2022, p. 198).

Layer II: Social Context and Discourse Analysis

Contextualization of the content of the meme instance within a social and historical context. This layer corresponds to Panofsky’s third level of interpretation of the symbolic and iconological meaning of an image and explores its “general cultural significance” (Rose, 2022, p. 199).

Layer III: Memetic Context and Discourse Analysis

Contextualization of the meme instance within its group and its relationship to other memes. Here, the specific significance of the meme in meme culture and its intertextual references to other memes are interpreted.

Layer IV: Linguistic Analysis

Description and analysis of linguistic mutations and strategies.

Summary and interpretation

A brief summary and synthesis of the above steps.

Multimodal discourse analysis was described by Kress & Van Leeuwen (2001). Reershemius uses the approach in her study of stickers in Birmingham (2019). Yoon (2016) applies it in her analysis of internet memes and racism. Kress & Van Leeuwen (2001)

sketch out four “domains of practice in which meanings are dominantly” made within multimodal discourse. These domains are discourse, design, production, and distribution. They are summarized by Kress and van Leeuwen as follows:

- Discourses are socially constructed knowledges of (some aspect of) reality.
- Designs are (uses of) semiotic resources, in all semiotic modes and combinations of semiotic modes.
- ‘Production’ refers to the organization of the expression, to the actual material articulation of the semiotic event or the actual material production of the semiotic artefact.
- Distribution refers to the technical ‘re-coding’ of semiotic products and events, for purposes of recording (e.g. tape recording, digital recording) and/or distribution (e.g. telephony, radio and television transmission).

Throughout this thesis, I use KnowYourMeme.com as it provides useful descriptions, context, examples and historical information about popular memes. I will shortly discuss the online databases and critiques of it.

4.5 Use of KnowYourMeme.com

KnowYourMeme.com has established itself over the years as *the* go-to source for historical information and research about memes and viral phenomena. Content can be contributed by the registered members of the website, but the website is a commercial venture with professional staff and owned by Literally Media Ltd., based in Seattle (‘About Know Your Meme’, 2024).

When working with information from KnowYourMeme.com, one has to keep in mind a) the commercial nature of the website and b) that the website is written in English and from an American perspective. Accordingly, there is a focus on English-language memes and American meme culture from an American point of view. Information about local, non-English memes is harder to come by. For example, there is no information on Swiss-German memes to be found on the website. Not even the two most popular Swiss meme accounts, @swissmeme and @hajdgenoss.ch, which receive regular press coverage in Switzerland, feature anywhere on the website. Searches for “Knorrli”, “Gring” and “Gölä” net no results. There are, however, several entries related to “Pingu”, the main character of a popular Swiss children’s show (e.g. ‘Noot Noot’, 2014).

Pettis (2022) warns that an “uncritical reliance on KYM’s definitions may overlook the polysemy of many memes.” Furthermore, he argues that the “overreliance on KYM as an authority on memes and their history can contribute to the homogenization of Web histories”. Nowotny & Reidy (2022), treating memes as (literary) texts, speak of a *canonization* of meme culture. This process, according to Nowotny & Reidy (2022), is not neutral and is shaped, at least partially, by canonizing institutions. They discuss KnowYourMeme.com in this regard (2022, pp. 183–190).

4.6 Justification of Methods

Image-type analysis was chosen because it combines a quantitative and qualitative approach. A large corpus of images can be ana-

lysed through content analysis, with the aim of identifying types. The promise of content analysis is that of a rigorous scientific process with reproducible and “objective” results (Rose, 2022). The method was indeed useful to approach the corpus from a critical distance. Setting clear criteria for corpus inclusion and applying a randomized sampling strategy, as suggested by Rose (2022) resulted in a less subjective selection of specimens and accounts to be analysed.

Multimodal discourse analysis was useful in establishing a framework for the qualitative analysis of the identified types. By combining the approach with the analytical framework used by Nowotny & Reidy (2022), I was able to adjust the method to my research questions.

I would choose these methods again. However, content analysis, especially the identification of categories and types, is very time-consuming. It is best done with the assistance of software such as QualCoder or MaxQDA. It took several analysis “runs” to develop types and coding rules. These then had to be verified by coding further randomized subsets. In the next project, it would be useful to define coding rules and types or categories together with other researchers. The results of coding sessions could then be compared, resulting in greater reproducibility and generalizability.

In this chapter, I have described the corpus criteria and the methods applied to analyze the corpus. Using a mixed quantitative and qualitative approach, types of language use were identified, and for each type, a specimen was qualitatively analysed and interpreted. Building on the Theoretical Framework and with the described methodology at hand, the next chapter documents the results of the analysis.

Types of memetic Swiss German mutations

Figure 26)
Overview of meme types,
by author, February 2024

"Haha du bisch 25 und wohnsch
immerno dihei. Bin scho sit 21 inere
WG :)"

Figure 27)
"WG" meme,
@hajdi.ch,
7 March 2020

5. Results

The results of my study show how multimodal communication, translation, and borrowing are playfully combined to achieve diverse communicative goals in Swiss memes. This chapter documents the analysis of the developed typology consisting of the types: “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Loan Words”, “Phonological Calques and Spelling”, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching” (Figure 26). For each type, a meme instance was analysed in detail.

5.1 Schwiizerdütsch

In “Schwiizerdütsch” memes, text is written in “pure” Swiss-German. This type of meme does not contain any recognizable loan words or calques. In the analysed sample of 167 memes, 32 memes featured text written purely in Swiss-German. Swiss-German was used for a variety of communicative purposes, ranging from banal statements to nonsensical shitposting. Frequently, Swiss-German was used to make fun of the language itself and of Swiss people, as the *Schnupfspruch* examples already showed. Mocking Swissness was a prevalent topic of Swiss-German memes in general and not unique to this type. Another source of humour was the use of Swiss-German in juxtaposition with non-Swiss contexts, e.g., when a dialect statement is placed next to an image of an American rapper. Figures 27-29 are examples of “Schwiizerdütsch” memes.

Figure 27 was more closely examined. The meme was not explicitly tied to any specific historical or social event. Its social significance was best understood in the context of the other memes typically posted on @hajdi.ch and @hajdgenoss (accounts operated by the same person). Most of the content posted on these accounts was based on the account creator’s experience of living in Switzerland as a “Usländer” (a foreigner/migrant). The text was translated as “Haha, you are 25 and still live at home. I have been living in a flat share since I was 21 :)”. Notably, the text was surrounded by quotation marks to mark the statement as a quote by a third and most likely Swiss person. With this context in mind, the meme was considered as part of the discourse surrounding immigration in Switzerland. Analysis of the memetic context revealed that the meme was not an instance of a particular meme group.

Formally, it was an instance of image macro memes, “captioned images that typically consist of a picture and a witty message or a catchphrase” (‘Image Macros’, 2012). A closer examination revealed that the meme used a format defined by the social media platform formerly known as Twitter. As such, it was an example of how platform affordances shape the aesthetics of content.

Figure 28 was an example of the juxtaposition of a banal Swiss-German statement with the photograph of American rapper 21 Savage. The former drug dealing gang member was pictured com-

i bi scho drbi we öpper mau mi
arbeitsplatz brucht weni nid da bi aber
chöiter bitte mi büroschtu nid zfescht
versteue schüschi hani wieder äckägstabi

Figure 28)
“Äckägstabi” meme,
@znueninaehmems,
11 March 2020

Figure 29)
“Löffu” meme,
@chnoeitoeif_im_
schissdraeck,
24 July 2020

plaining about getting a stiff neck because somebody had readjusted his office chair. Figure 29 was another instance of the Knorrli meme and was situated completely in a Swiss context. The text was a figure of speech popular in German and was translated as “Whoever is not up in the trees by the count of three, will “get” my spoon”.

Most memes are highly ironic in nature, and Swiss-German memes are no exception. In “Schwiizerdütsch” memes, the butt of the joke frequently was the language itself as well as Swiss people. Considering that the corpus consisted mostly of memes that use Swiss-German, examples of “Schwiizerdütsch” were actually not widely spread. Both in everyday spoken and written Swiss-German, loan words are widely used.

5.2 Loan words, phonological calques and spelling

Memes of the type “Loan Word” were the biggest group in the analyzed sample. In this type, words were borrowed from other languages and used in Swiss-German. In the analyzed sample, words were mostly borrowed from English, but French and other languages were also borrowing sources. I have conflated the types “loan word” and “phonological calque and spelling” here, as the second type consisted entirely of loan words that were phonologically spelled. Another meme posted by @znueninaehmems was analyzed more closely for multimodal and linguistic properties as well as for its place in memetic and social discourse. The meme was chosen as an example of “Loan Word” memes for its borrowing of a term rooted in AAVE.

The meme in Figure 30 was not only an example of borrowing AAVE terms; it was surprisingly connected to LGBTQ+ discourse. A close inspection of the used photograph of a starfish revealed that it was heavily distorted, both in shape and color saturation. The distortion applied was characteristic of “deepfried” memes popular at the time. The text at the top contained a Swiss short form of the name Patrick, “pädu”, as well as an AAVE slang term, “thicc”. The text was translated as “Patrick, why so voluptuous?”. The use of the word “thicc” could have been interpreted as sexist objectifying of women or perpetuating a male gaze. However, this first interpretation was subverted by the fact that the depicted starfish was referred to by a typically male name. A connection to LGBTQ+ discourse was revealed by a closer examination of the memetic context. The meme was an instance of a) the SpongeBob SquarePants meme and b) the “Thicc Starfish” meme (‘Thicc Starfish’, 2019). Three months after the @znueninaehmems post discussed here, a Twitter post by Nickelodeon seemingly outed SpongeBob as gay. In a June 2020 post in celebration of “Pride Month”, a picture of Spongebob in front of a rainbow flag was included. This was interpreted by some sources as an “official” outing of Spongebob as gay, and the hashtag #SpongeBobsGay started trending (France, 2020).

The slang term “thicc”, “used to describe the voluptuous, hour-glass-like curvature of a woman’s hips” is rooted in AAVE and hip-hop culture (‘Thicc’, 2016). The inclusion of a dark-skinned emoji was interpreted as confirming the connection to African-American culture.

Figure 31 was another example of a loan word from another language than English used in Swiss-German memes, in this case

pädu wieso so thicc 🙄🔥🙏

Figure 30)
"Thicc" meme,
@znueninaehmems,
5 March 2020

Figure 31)
"Mashalla" meme,
@secondomeme,
28 July 2020

EXGÜSSI FÜR D'STÖRIG ABER HÄTTE SIE SCHNÄLL ZYT
ZUM MIT UNS ÜBER UNSERE HEILIGE ERLÖSER Z'REDE?

Figure 32)
"Exgüssi" meme,
@stewia2046,
11 March 2020

“Mashalla” from Arabic. Figure 32 was an example of a phonological calque. “Exgüssi” is a phonological loan translation of the French “excusez” (‘Äxgüsi’, 2018). It was an example of how sometimes old-timey expressions were ironically used in Swiss-German memes and thus both replicated and conserved.

Memes of the “Loan Word” and “Phonological Calque and Spelling” types were prevalent in the analysed sample. While English was the most frequent source language, words borrowed from French (e.g. “mère”, “gourmet” or “Kontrolleur”) were also identified. The meme discussed above confirmed the influence of American pop culture and African-American culture on meme culture. In memes of the discussed types, words are directly borrowed or phonologically spelled in Swiss-German. A more complex form of borrowing is phraseological calque, or literal translation.

5.3 Literal Translations

In memes of the “Literal Translations” type, linguistic structures are directly translated to the target language, keeping the grammatical structure of the source language. In the analysed sample, six instances of literal translations were identified. While literal translations were rare, they confirmed the influence of meme culture on Swiss-German, at least for the analysed corpus. When structures were literally translated to Swiss-German, they were often catchphrases prevalent in meme culture and on social media in general. For the “Literal Translation” meme type, an example posted by @jesus.nr1 (Figure 33) was analysed, which echoed the discussion on folklore, its sometimes obscene nature, and the tension between “fixity and novelty” (Milner, 2013).

The meme in Figure 33 was clearly classified as a shitpost for its discordant stance, and as an example of the grotesque aesthetic described in *Theoretical Framework*. Multiple communication modes such as background color, a distorted photograph and text were combined. Central to the composition was an image of far-right Swiss politician Erich Hess, whose head was transformed to resemble that of a dog. Hess was and still is a popular figure¹ in Swiss meme culture. Despite featuring a politician, the meme communicates no explicit political message. A close reading of the memetic context revealed that each communication mode was referencing formal memetic conventions. Formally, the meme was an instance of Advice Animals (‘Advice Animals’, 2011). The conventions of the format however were “violated” in multiple ways. The background in Advice Animals memes were conventionally symmetrical and emanated from the center of the image. The top text was conventionally used to setup a joke or situation, while the bottom text delivered the punchline. In the meme at hand, the punchline of the purposely unfunny joke was delivered right at the top, while the bottom text inanely contained an appeal to “like und comment”. The background was asymmetrical. Closer inspection of the transformed revealed that it was shaped to resemble Kabosu, a shiba inu breed dog and the main character of “Doge” memes (‘Doge’, 2013). This was read as another violation of the Advice Animals convention, as Doge was not usually featured in the format. The result of these violations was highly ironic. The meme at hand was making a statement about other memes and about people using outworn memetic templates and repeating the same

¹ The term figure is fitting here, as recurring characters in jokes are called *Witzfiguren*, “joke figures” in German.

Figure 33)
 "Gring" shitpost,
 @jesus.nr1,
 4 February 2021

Figure 34)
 "Gring" meme,
 @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck,
 17 November 2020

Figure 35)
 "Gring" meme,
 @sexgruesel,
 1 July 2020

jokes and memes. Finally, the meme was analysed as a representation of the “literal translation” type because of the word “GRING”. “Gring” memes were popular in Swiss-German meme culture during the Covid pandemic, as multiple examples in the corpus show. At first glance, “gring” (‘Gring’, 2018) was simply a translation of “head”. Closer inspection revealed that “Gring” memes derived their - puerile - humour from the fact that “getting / giving head” is English slang for receiving / performing oral sex.

Figures 34 and 35 were further examples of “Gring” memes. The top text in Figure 34 translated to “Who wants to get head?”, while the bottom text translated to “Who wants to give head?” In Figure 35 the statement at the bottom was translated as “What do you mean by”no head”?”. Figures 37 and 38 are further examples of literal translations from English to Swiss-German. In Figure 37, the AAVE term “no cap” was literally translated to “Kei Chappe”¹. To “cap” means “to lie, boast or to front” (‘Word We’re Watching’, 2024), whereas “no cap” signifies telling the truth. In Figure 38 the phrase “wenn du nussisch” was a phraseological calque of “when you nut” (“busting a nut” being AAVE slang for ejaculating and *Nuss* German for “nut”).

In many “Literal Translation” memes, the influence of meme culture, English, and AAVE on Swiss-German became evident. Such phraseological calques were exploited for word play in Swiss-German. Especially in the genre of shitposting, literal translations formed the basis for bawdy inside jokes that appealed to a smaller collective. For the discussion of the “Code Switching” type, we will remain in the genre.

5.4 Code Switching

In memes that employ code switching, languages are switched within the same meme, sometimes in the middle of sentences. In the analyzed sample, I have coded 25 specimens for this type. A shitpost by @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck (Figure 36) was analysed for this type.

In Figure 36, three main communication modes were combined: text, photography and visible corrections. Just as in the “Literal Translation” example, there were no explicit political messages or references to current affairs identifiable. Instead, the meme was contributing to memetic discourse by making a statement about the nature of shitposting: “ig in the shitpost sitä like yeah this cheggt niemer u närvt aui”, which was translated as “Me in the shitpost page like: noone will get this and it will irritate everyone”. The English text of the exploited image/template was corrected using black strokes. Judging from the typeface and the digital pencil strokes, Instagram’s story editor was used to create the image. The meme was an instance of the “Drop It” meme (‘In the Studio Like, “Drop It”, 2020). The man in the center of the photograph was African-American rapper Young Thug.

The post at hand was chosen for analysis because it was an example of visual, multimodal code switching. Parts of the English catchphrase were scribbled over in black, leaving only “in the”, “like”, “yeah this” and “drop it” visible. The scribbles created visual and structural gaps in the phrase, which were filled with the

¹ Credits to @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck for inspiring the title of my thesis and to Young Thug, who was, among others, credited for popularizing the phrase “no cap” (‘Word We’re Watching’, 2024).

Figure 36)
 “Drop it” shitpost,
 @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck,
 18 September 2020

Figure 37)
 “No cap” shitpost,
 @chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck,
 28 July 2020

Figure 38)
 “Wenn du nussisch” shitpost,
 @slimettos,
 28 March 2020

Swiss-German “ig”, “shitpost sitä” (“shitpost” constituting a loan word), “cheggt niemer” and “u närvt aui”.

Figures 39 and 40 are further examples of visual code switching practiced in Swiss-German memes. In Figure 39, the post is started with an English sentence structure (“I may show it through my incessant and sporadic shitposting”), which was ended with a mixed English/Swiss-German structure (“but i bi huere hobbylos”, which contained the loan word “hobby” and was translated as “but I very much don’t have any hobbies / am hobbyless”). In Figure 39 parts of the original meme were scribbled over multiple times to make room for inserting Swiss-German. Figure 40 contrasts the discussed shitposts about shitposting and carries an explicit, political message. It contributes to the discourse surrounding human rights¹. In Figure 40 codes were switched multiple times, as the below listing shows:

- English: “DON’T MAKE ME TAP THE SIGN.”
- Swiss-German: “ischs e mönsch?” (“is it a human being?”)
- French: “voilà” (“there you have it”)
- Swiss-German: “mönscherächt” (“human rights”)
- English: “apply”

In monomodal forms of code switching, the communication mode is limited to, e.g., speech or text. In memes of the type analysed here, visual techniques were applied to achieve a mix of languages within the same expression. The importance of multimodality in memetic media came to the fore and was playfully exploited. “Code Switching” and “Literal Translations” constituted the most complex Swiss-German “mutations” I have identified. Both types require fluency in at least two languages and knowledge of memetic conventions. Furthermore, the direct influence or inspiration of English, meme culture, and AAVE became most evident in these two types.

5.5 Modes of Communication

In the analysed sample, a number of main communication modes were identified and listed below.

- Photograph
- Text
- Emoji
- Emoticon
- Distortion
- Background
- Corrections

The combination of photographs, text-based emoticons, image-based emoji, and text is “par for the course” for image memes. And for advertising, as I have demonstrated in the Introduction. More interesting was the frequent use of visual distortion techniques such as over-saturation, compression, or excessive cropping. Furthermore, some specimens contained visible traces of corrections or substitutions made to the source image. Both corrections and distortions were treated as communication modes, as they were

¹ As does the Operation Libero meme mentioned in the Literature Review.

Figure 39)
“Hobbylos” shitpost,
@chline_hutzu,
9 February 2021

Figure 40)
“Mönscherächt” meme,
@pouletbruschthirni,
21 February 2021

judged to serve one or more communicative purposes. These purposes will be interpreted in the Discussion.

In this chapter, I have documented the findings of my analysis. These results will be interpreted and used to answer the research questions in the next, penultimate chapter.

6. Discussion

To contribute to the barely existing research on Swiss meme culture, I have analysed a corpus of image memes posted on Instagram during the COVID-19 pandemic. I was interested in finding out how Swiss-German was used in the corpus (RQ1), what types of language use could be identified (RQ2) and how multimodal communication affects language use (RQ3). In this chapter, I will discuss the key findings, limitations, and implications of my research.

6.1 Use of Swiss-German in Image Memes posted on Instagram

The influence of American and African-American pop culture and the notion that “internet culture depends on Black people” (Jackson, 2016) was evident in the analysed corpus and had a direct impact on language use. Memes are a largely, if not exclusively, “Western” phenomenon (Milner, 2016; Nissenbaum & Shifman, 2018) and they “may serve as powerful agents of globalization and Americanization” (Shifman et al., 2014). When words and expressions are borrowed and translated in Swiss-German memes, the source is mostly American English and frequently AAVE. The influence of African American culture is best explained by the global reach of rap, trap, drill, and related hip-hop music genres.

Regarding Swiss meme culture, this raises questions that should be investigated in further research. Are Swiss memes simply adaptations of international, mostly American conventions? What is Swiss about Swiss memes? Does it matter? Of course, the topics, iconography and discourse present in Swiss memes are often specifically Swiss. And the focus of this thesis is another distinguishing quality of Swiss memes: the use of Swiss-German, a language that is spoken by merely 0.06 percent of the global population¹.

6.2 Typology of Swiss-German Mutations

My main research interest has been to investigate *how* Swiss-German is used in image memes posted on Instagram. In the following discussion, I will focus on the meme types “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching”. These types are arguably the most complex sources of vernacular creativity in Swiss-German memes, while the latter two types are the ones most intertwined with and influenced by meme culture. Furthermore, they differ quite strongly from everyday Swiss-German.

In memes of the “Schwiizerdütsch” type, Swiss-German is, mainly ironically, used for three main communicative purposes. Firstly, Swiss-German is juxtaposed against a non-Swiss context, for ex-

¹ Calculated on the basis 5 million Swiss-German speakers and a world population of 8 billion people (‘Swiss-German’, 2024; ‘World Population’, 2024).

ample by having African-American rappers “say” banal things in Swiss-German dialect. Swiss-German, which Swiss people sometimes self-consciously regard as an “uncool” farmer language (De l’Horizon, 2022), is juxtaposed in such memes against the “aura and global appeal of hip-hop” which is perceived as “hip, stylish” and “rebellious” according to Tate (2003). In these memes, the Swiss-German vernacular itself becomes the subject of ironic memetic mockery. Secondly, Swiss-German is used to make fun of Swiss people, specifically the conservative, boring, and uptight *Bünzli* (in American jazz slang, a “square” (‘Square (Slang)’, 2023). In such memes, Swiss-German is used to imitate how a *Bünzli* would think or talk about things. Thirdly, some memes use Swiss-German simply to make a statement or tell a joke, without making a statement *about* Swiss-German or Swiss people.

When Swiss sayings and old-timey expressions become subject of memesis, they are both conserved and revitalized. Terms such as “Äxgüsi”¹ or “Äckägstabi”² and characters like the wrinkly “Hutzü”³, the slothful “Laueri”⁴, and the dreaded “Sexgrüsel”⁵ all get revitalized by being included in and spread by memes. This finding is another indicator of the folkloric character of memes and the interplay of dynamism and conservation (Nowotny & Reidy, 2022), fixity and novelty (Milner, 2016).

The meme types “Schwiizerdütsch”, “Loan Words” and “Phonological Calque & Spelling” mostly reflect everyday spoken and written Swiss-German. They are also evident in literary texts and advertisement campaigns. Sometimes, loan words are subcultural signifiers, e.g., the use of rock and blues slang in Frank (2023) and the use of hip-hop slang in many Swiss-German memes. The use of loan words, specifically anglicisms, is prevalent in Swiss-German and not unique to meme culture.

Of the developed typologies, “Literal Translation” and “Code Switching” memes most strongly expose the influence of meme culture on Swiss-German use in memes. In these meme types, expressions and words prevalent in memetic discourse are literally translated to or calqued in Swiss-German. “Code Switching” and “Literal Translation” memes, I argue, are a potential source for new slang and expressions introduced into Swiss-German. It is not improbable that literally translated expressions such as “kei chappe” (“no cap”), “mis gsicht wenn” (“my face when”) or “gring gä” (“giving head”) spread into everyday spoken Swiss-German *because* they were popularized in memes. It is also easy to imagine switching, in speech and in writing, from Swiss-German to English memetic catchphrases such as “I am once again asking”, “all my homies hate” or “guys really live like this”. A case in point: “hip” and “cool” are rooted in African-American Vernacular English and the jazz subculture. Who could have predicted these terms becoming fully integrated into Standard English and being borrowed by countless other languages? Arguably, meme culture is already influencing language use. Judging from personal observations, words and turns of phrase popularized by memes are already used

¹ A calque of the French “excusez” (‘Äxgüsi’, 2018)

² A stiff neck (‘Äckegschtabi’, 2018)

³ An old, wrinkly and tiny person (‘Hutzelmanndli, Hutzelfroueli’, 2018)

⁴ A wasteful “never-do-well” (‘Laueri’, 2018)

⁵ A pervert (‘Grüsel’, 2018)

in Swiss-German. Still, at this point I only have tentative speculation, comparison, and anecdotal evidence to offer.

“Code Switching” memes bring me to a final consideration of multimodality. In some of the memes analysed, languages are switched visually, by combining communication modes. In these memes, the original template or source image is at the same time made explicit and “vandalized”. The result of combining Swiss-German with English sentence fragments is often quite nonsensical. Such playful language switching, I argue, also bears a literary quality, calling to mind the inventive Swiss-German writing by Oppliger (2018) and Frank (2023). “Wie dir sirche usgseht weder my shit double tapped”¹ (Figure 42) “My bro lean said i hät no viu blöder tah”² (Figure 41) and “Everyone is so stuck up into gölä memes sch herte cringe bro”³ (Figure 43) are surreal concoctions that would not at all be out of place in post-modern Swiss literary writing, next to sentences such as “merhei di nöi fämmorrison glost usisch xi wie wemen uf schit ifart”⁴ (Frank, 2023, p. 32) or “umpmänsche xänzimli spuuki uus”⁵ (Oppliger, 2018, p. 89).

6.3 Modes of Communication

Corrections in “Code Switching” memes are often made in an amateurish fashion by carelessly “scribbling” over parts of the original image. Image memes, especially shitposts, differ from professional communication; the amateurish, “poor image” aesthetic is essential to them and is celebrated even. These memes are supposed to look as if they were created in a careless, spontaneous act of creativity. I have identified and described amateurish corrections, willful oversaturation, and unnecessary compression as a discrete communication mode. Indeed, such distortion is essential to image-based shitposting and the genre of deep-fried memes. The can be compared to rock music: the same song can be played on an acoustic guitar or on an electric guitar with distortion applied. The effect is entirely different. Distortion and overdrive effects are essential to “heavy metal” music genres, just as distortion is essential to deep-fried memes. But what is the effect of applying such an unnecessary yet essential distortion to image-based memes? That fundamental stance of most memes, irony, seems to be the key here. Distortion has the following effects:

- It demarcates shitposts and deepfried memes from “clean” mainstream memes
- It signifies an ironic distance to the content of a meme
- It is confusing to people who are not familiar with the conventions of the genre
- It demonstrates technical prowess and inside knowledge

These thoughts on irony are a point of departure for further research and discussion. In fact, a lot has been written on irony in memes already.

¹ “How you guys look when you like my content (on Instagram)”

² “My friend”Lean” said I would have acted a fool more”, a reference to the hit song “I Hätt No Viu Blöder Ta” by Gölä

³ Another Gölä reference, which translates to “Everyone is so stuck up into Gölä memes, it’s really cringe, bro”

⁴ “We listened to the new Van Morrison record and it was like taking heroin”

⁵ “and the people look pretty spooky”

Figure 41)
 “My bro lean” code switching meme,
 @jesus.nr1,
 16 March 2020

Figure 42)
 “Dir sirche” code switching meme,
 @mondhausi,
 21 October 2020

Figure 43)
 “Stuck up into gölä” code switching meme,
 @chline_hutzu,
 23 October 2020

The connections I have made to literary writing and the importance of aesthetics call to mind the somewhat provocative notes by Nowotny & Reidy (2022) on memes and so-called *Hochkultur* (serious or “highbrow” culture) (p. 189-190), which I will paraphrase from German. Memes are often viewed as trivial products of “low culture”. Meanwhile, the enjoyment of the products of *Hochkultur* is seen as requiring a distinguished, educated aesthetic stance and a particular cultural competency on the side of the recipients. There is a supposed “right” way of enjoying the products of *Hochkultur*. If we follow these thoughts, so Nowotny & Reidy (2022), the same can be said for memes. Just like “serious” (bourgeois, perhaps?) works of art, they are autonomous artifacts, setting their own formal norms and they connect to existing cultural material in complex, referential relationships (2022, pp. 189–190). Their “proper” enjoyment presupposes a cultural competency. Memetically “schooled” viewers demarcate themselves from “Normies” who only consume outdated memes on mainstream platforms such as Facebook and 9GAG (p. 190). These thoughts by Nowotny & Reidy (2022), coarsely paraphrased here, connect seamlessly to the discussion of memes and literacy education by Knobel & Lankshear (2007, p. 219 - 225). “Contributing a multimodal” meme text”, so Knobel & Lankshear (2007), “regardless of the actual absurdity of the content [...] requires a range of finely honed technical skills and competencies.” As my thesis and the absurd examples throughout show, it is not only technical skills that are required, but also linguistic, communicative and cultural competencies, both on the side of the creators and the enjoyers of memes.

Above, I have highlighted some of the key findings of my research. In the following, I will discuss its limitations and make recommendations for further research on Swiss meme culture.

6.4 Limitations

The account list used as a basis for selecting the corpus of memes for this study is somewhat subjective. There is a bias towards memes written in Bernese dialect, posted by politically left-leaning and progressive meme creators. However, the methodology and the corpus criteria allowed for critical distance to and a more objective view of the analysed memes. Owing to the small size of the samples analyzed, the generalizability of my results is limited. Further research should be conducted to see if the developed typology could be applied to a corpus of memes from another language and how the results compare to my analysis. It would be interesting to find out whether loan words, code switching and literal translations are prevalent in other vernacular meme cultures, too.

The corpus is testament to an active subculture of Swiss meme creators on Instagram, but it is not representative of Swiss meme culture at large. Swiss memes posted on online forums, websites, Facebook, TikTok, or Reddit were not included in the corpus. By focusing on Swiss-German, Swiss memes written in the three national languages of French, Italian, and Romansh have been ignored, as well as Swiss memes written in German and other languages.

6.5 Recommendations for Research on Swiss Meme Culture

The limitations of my research show that there is much room for more. As of 2024, there is still little to no research on Swiss meme culture. At this point, I want to humbly offer three recommendations for future research.

Research grounded in cultural studies and postcolonial theory could focus on topics such as racial stereotyping and cultural appropriation in Swiss memes. What is happening when African-American Vernacular English “meets” with Swiss-German in memes? What power dynamics are at play? Are concepts such as hybridity and third spaces useful in understanding these dynamics?

Swiss memes could be included in or compared to linguistic research on Swiss-German writing practices. Take, for example, the “What’s Up, Switzerland?” project which deals with a corpus of 763’644 WhatsApp chat messages in the four national languages (Ueberwasser & Stark, 2017). Could the typology developed for this thesis be used to categorize Swiss-German use in text messaging? Does language use in Swiss memes differ from it? Can the influence of meme culture be traced in everyday chat messages?

Research on the visual rhetoric of Swiss memes may shed light on the representation and framing of “Swissness”. What iconography is used in memes to represent Swiss culture and identity? Why do some Instagram meme accounts such as @swissmeme, @sad-memesschiiz or @suisseromandelibre explicitly mention nationality in their names? What discourse is there on Swissness in these memes? And, again: What is Swiss about Swiss memes?

As I have shown with my study, a look through the memetic keyhole can provide insights into current affairs, communication and language use. Further inquiry and documentation of the phenomenon are required. My research, and meme studies in general, attest to the fact that memes are more than a trivial fad. I hope my findings and the above recommendations may serve as inspiration for future research on Swiss meme culture.

7. Conclusion

There are many layers to *how* Swiss-German is used in image memes on Instagram. Swiss-German is used ironically to make fun of Switzerland, its celebrities, folklore, mascots, and politicians, and of the Swiss-German vernacular itself. Swiss-German is mutated and transformed by creatively translating, borrowing, and calquing expressions from other languages. Mostly, these other languages are English and African-American vernacular English. AAVE, hip-hop culture, rap music, through their unprecedented global reach, not only influence the *lingua franca* of the internet but also the unruly Swiss-German, the language of farmers and *Bünzli*. Another force acting on how Swiss-German is used in memes is multimodality. Multimodally, Swiss-German text is visually mixed with the catchphrases of existing memes. The result are brand new sentences, often nonsensical, sometimes quite literary in nature. Multimodality is a logic shared with professional advertisements; in memes, however, it is used for entirely unprofessional purposes. Excessive saturation and compression constitute another layer of irony to some Swiss memes and shitposts. Grotesque distortion constitutes a communicative mode in and of itself. The result of all these influences and forces and the mixing, transforming, and translating of cultural material are digital artifacts that echo the bawdy and amateurish nature of folkloristic practices.

Writing this master's thesis was a very rewarding, intense, and instructive experience. It has allowed me to delve into the inner workings of language and memes, two subjects that have fascinated me for a long time. I first came across memes in viral email messages, message boards, and chat rooms while surfing the World Wide Web of the early 2000s. No Google, no search engine optimization, and no corporate social media platforms in sight—just people writing hypertext in Notepad.exe. Having followed internet memes for so long, they indeed are folklore to me. It is fascinating to see the many forms internet memes take today and the cultural and even political significance and influence they have gained.

Writing and researching this thesis also posed challenges. Learning the do's and don'ts of academic writing was daunting. I am an IT professional, not an academic. Writing with a three-fold target audience of people unfamiliar with meme culture, esteemed meme scholars, and sarcastic meme creators in mind was sometimes nerve-racking. I have also learned a lesson about the importance of well-formulated, precise research questions. The questions helped me regain focus when I went down another rabbit hole, but I simply had too many of them. In my research proposal, I set out with eight questions. Three questions remain, addressing only the essential aspects of what I actually wanted to find out and document. Overall, I am thankful for the challenges the writing of a master's thesis poses. I have learned a lot from taking them on,

and I am happy with the result. And I would like to again state my gratitude to Idil and Baldo, who always made time to give feedback and answer my questions.

With my thesis, I address a gap in research on internet memes in Switzerland. In order to address this lack of research, I have focused on an aspect of Swiss memes that is uniquely Swiss: the use of Swiss-German. My findings document how Swiss-German is used in image memes, how meme culture influences it, and how dialect writing in memes relates to literature and advertising. By writing in English and not in *Hochdeutsch*, I address a wider audience and make Swiss meme culture accessible to people who do not speak Swiss-German. I restate my hope that my work may inspire more research - and that I get to conduct some of it. Priis!

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10. Appendix A: Tools & Workflows

Software Tools

This section is used for documentation of the software tools used to write this thesis and to collect data for the corpus.

Pandoc

The thesis was written in markdown files and converted to PDF using Pandoc (MacFarlane, 2006). The workflow and configuration used are based on documentation by Terence Eden Eden (2022).

4CAT Capture and Analysis Toolkit

The 4CAT Capture and Analysis Toolkit is “a software suite that can capture data from a variety of online sources and analyze the data through analytical processors. 4CAT is developed by OILab and the Digital Methods Initiative at the University of Amsterdam” (Digitalmethodsinitiative/4cat, 2024). 4CAT was used together with Zeeschuimer and Foxscroller to capture data from Instagram.

I have followed the official 4CAT documentation for installing it using Docker (‘Installing 4CAT’, 2024) . Under Settings > Download images, I have increased the limit to 5000 images.

Zeeschuimer

I have used the browser extension “Zeeschuimer” to collect Instagram posts. In fact, it was the only solution that worked for collecting these data, and the research conducted would not have been possible without 4CAT and Zeeschuimer. “Zeeschuimer” was developed by the Digital Methods Initiative (DMI).

Zeeschuimer is a browser extension that monitors internet traffic while you are browsing a social media site and collects data about the items you see in a platform’s web interface for later systematic analysis. Its target audience is researchers who wish to systematically study content on social media platforms that resist conventional scraping or API-based data collection. (Digitalmethodsinitiative/Zeeschuimer, 2024)

FoxScroller

FoxScroller is an add-on for the Firefox web browser. It is used to automatically scroll to the bottom of a page. I used it to find out the dates of the first posts of the accounts in my corpus. Together with Zeeschuimer, it was used to capture the content of selected Instagram accounts. Zeeschuimer is capturing data as soon as the page is scrolled.

Bash

Bash is a shell language and command-line environment for Unix and GNU/Linux-based operating systems. It is useful for command-line-based manipulation of files, texts, and processes. I have used Bash scripts and commands to mass rename the files in the corpus, for counting characters, and to create randomized sample selections from the overall corpus. Useful commands and scripts developed to solve certain problems are documented here for completeness and later reference's sake.

4catrenamer.sh

I have written `4catrenamer.sh` to make the names of the image files downloaded with 4CAT human-readable. Additionally, the script performs cleanup tasks such as removing duplicate files and metadata and converting all images from png to jpg. The script looks up the file in a table of metadata shipped with all 4CAT downloads. From this table, the time stamp, author, and unique Instagram ID of the image are read. These are then used to generate a new filename in the format `20200618-183236-sexgruesel-CBlix-a8JL-C.jpg`. The original files are preserved, and the renamed files are copied to a separate directory.

selecter.sh

I have developed the `selecter.sh` script to copy all the image files that were created in the date range defined for the corpus to a new directory.

selectfromaccount.sh

The `selectfromaccount.sh` script copies five random image files from each account in the corpus to a new directory. The copied selection is used as a basis for content analysis in QualCoder.

Workflows

Capturing Instagram Data with 4CAT and Zeeschuimer

Below, you can find documentation for how to capture Instagram data using 4CAT and the Zeeschuimer browser extension. Additionally, the extension FoxScroller was used to automate scrolling of the page.

Capturing Instagram posts

- Open Zeeschuimer in Firefox
- Define the 4CAT server URL (`http://localhost:1337`)
- Open the Instagram page to be captured in another browser tab
- In Zeeschuimer, set Instagram (Posts) to “Active” under “Captured data objects”
- If there are items listed under “Items” from a previous capture, click “Delete” or “Delete all items” to remove them
- Switch to the Instagram profile and start scrolling using FoxScroller
- Once the bottom of the page is reached, go back to Zeeschuimer.

- Verify that the number of captured items correspond to the number of posts listed on the Instagram profile
- Under “Captured data objects”, click the 4CAT action button
- Disable the capture of Instagram posts

Posts are now uploaded to 4CAT. Under “Connect to 4CAT” you can track the progress of the import.

Downloading posts and metadata

- Once the upload is complete, click on the “View Dataset” link
- Change the description from “Instagram Dataset to the account’s name
- Create a directory with the accounts name in the same directory as the other account directories, e.g.,/accounts/poulet-bruschthirni
- In the dataset view of 4CAT (Datasets -> Analysis), download the csv file under “Result” and save it in the account’s directory
- Rename the file with the date and account name, e.g. 2023-12-29-pouletbruschthirni.csv
- In the 4CAT dataset view, scroll down to “Visual” and click on “Options” next to “Download images”
- Increase the number of images to be bigger than the number of captured posts
- Leave the other options as they are and click on “Run”

The images are now being downloaded, and you can track the status at the top under “Analysis results”.

- Under “Analysis results”, click on zip to download the collected images
- Move the zip archive to the account’s directory and rename it with the date and account name, e.g. 2023-12-29-pouletbruschthirni.zip
- Extract the zip archive and rename the new directory to “src”

Processing downloaded 4CAT data with 4catrenamer.sh

Once you have downloaded the desired account’s post, there is some processing necessary in order to work with the data.

- In Bash, change to the directory containing the accounts
- Run the 4catrenamer.sh script, specifying the account’s directory and csv file as arguments.

Check the account’s directory. It should now contain a directory called “renamed”.

Selecting images fitting the corpus criteria

Once you have downloaded the desired posts from 4CAT and processed them using 4catrenamer.sh, the posts fitting the criteria set for the corpus need to be filtered out. For this, selector.sh can be used.

- In Bash, change to the directory containing the accounts
- Run the selector.sh script, specifying the account’s directory as the argument.

Verifying downloaded data

After downloading and processing the posts, verify the data. Verify that the number of files corresponds to the reported number of posts on the Instagram profile page. The number will not be the same, as for slide posts (posts containing multiple images), only the first post is downloaded.

To partially automate verification of the downloaded and processed files, `stichprob.sh` and `verify.sh` can be used.

- In Bash, change to the directory containing the accounts
- In the account's directory, check the `rename.log` for any errors
- Run `verify.sh`, giving the account's directory as an argument.

`verify.sh` will compare the number of source files to the number of renamed files to give an indication if something went wrong.

- Run `stichprob.sh`, giving the account's "renamed" directory as the argument.

`stichprob.sh` will open six random image files (with `eog` / Eye Of Gnome on Debian/Linux) and, additionally, the corresponding Instagram post in your browser. This way, you can verify that the renamed files match an actual Instagram post.

Creating a randomized sample from the corpus

Content analysis on all of the downloaded files is not feasible. Instead, I was working with a sample that consists of five randomly selected files per account in the corpus. This subset can be generated using `selectfromaccount.sh`.

- In Bash, change to the directory containing the accounts
- Run `selectfromaccount.sh` with the directory containing the accounts as the argument

11. Appendix B: List of Swiss Meme Pages

I have started compiling a list of Swiss Instagram meme pages in 2021, which you will find on the following pages. The list forms the basis for corpus selection. Criteria for inclusion were checked in September 2023. It is by no way a complete list of all Swiss Instagram meme pages. Due to technical reasons, it is included in a separate Appendix.

Account name	Latest post	First Post	Language
1sad_bitch_at_1am	21.03.23	27.05.21	CH
bielbiennepleger	01.09.23	28.03.23	CH
biraeweich	01.09.22	25.12.20	CH
biukinibottom	06.07.21	15.03.21	CH
blarmeme_de_wartensee	17.08.23	09.09.20	FR
brainrottperversion	02.09.23	31.05.21	CH
bundesamt.fuer.memes	04.12.21	27.10.20	CH
bundesrat.ch	13.07.23	28.12.20	CH
caramelgring	07.08.23	05.01.23	CH
cesmemespasdroles	05.09.23	17.12.20	FR
chline_hutzu	07.06.23	21.10.20	CH
chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck	31.08.19	23.07.20	CH
chreger420	06.03.22	20.01.22	CH
chrueppuhund	16.03.22	07.02.21	CH
cringe_movement	03.02.22	24.10.21	CH
cybermartullo187	29.11.20	31.07.20	CH
dachshoden	02.09.21	07.11.19	CH
departementfuerschwarzemedien	0	01.05.20	CH
draindler.page	04.09.23	26.01.20	CH
esgaschowisse	05.07.21	16.04.21	CH
figghounds	19.06.22	18.10.20	CH
figgstuebli	11.06.23	11.10.21	CH
fleischbby	17.11.22	27.07.21	EN
fleischgwuerz	16.03.22	28.02.22	CH
fuchspescha	29.03.22	29.03.22	CH
furztroche	0	N/A	N/A
gagugauge	07.09.23	06.12.20	CH
gahtsno.memes	23.09.21	10.09.21	CH
globi_ledig_sucht_gugor	08.10.21	09.02.21	CH
gluengi_und_e_suermu	03.09.23	22.05.21	CH
gopferdammysiech	01.04.23	21.06.21	CH
gubimeme	02.10.22	29.06.22	CH
haha.doggo	05.09.23	15.07.17	EN
hajdgenoss	05.09.23	13.04.14	CH

Account name	Latest post	First Post	Language
hajdi.ch	03.09.23	24.01.17	CH
harzbergen	08.07.23	11.05.21	CH
hetsno.memes	03.07.23	29.04.20	CH
houndgagel	25.07.22	02.10.21	CH
hypermemeality	18.07.23	29.02.20	CH
i_dis_gzicht	24.08.23	18.12.21	CH
iademerci	05.01.23	13.12.21	CH
ichverchaufememes	02.09.23	24.01.19	EN
intellectuals_basel	21.07.23	19.10.21	EN
jesus.nr1	04.09.23	08.11.15	CH
jusomemebase	21.12.21	03.04.19	CH
kassensturzcollectuals	16.08.21	12.08.21	CH
keineweiss1312	12.12.21	30.11.21	CH
klaebmibabbe	05.09.23	08.09.21	CH
koksstattbeton	03.08.22	07.11.20	CH
lauericheib69	03.09.23	31.08.20	CH
leffelpueski	15.04.23	09.12.21	CH
les_rois_du_cheni	29.08.23	18.09.20	FR
liberouchoupichou	30.08.23	30.11.20	FR
linkefotzen	03.09.23	25.01.21	CH
loesch.ch	28.09.23	23.02.19	CH
mani.matter.si.fatter	14.06.23	20.02.22	CH
memecheib	08.09.22	17.10.20	CH
memhio	09.02.23	08.04.18	CH
memu.memes	08.03.21	04.09.20	CH
mennerslol.ch	27.04.22	28.05.21	CH
mettugring420	07.10.22	16.07.20	CH
mmp_memes	17.04.23	04.03.20	CH
mondhausi	22.08.23	26.07.20	CH
muetersduemmst_official	29.08.23	19.10.20	CH
neoliberali666	14.01.22	08.10.21	CH
peino_inhalt	07.08.20	30.07.20	CH
pouletbruschthirni	02.09.23	18.02.21	CH
riisegigu	01.09.23	27.11.22	CH
sadmemesschwiiz	06.09.23	21.03.20	CH
salzmann.tinu	25.02.23	30.08.20	CH
samanthathic	25.08.23	13.06.18	CH
schnaebmemes	28.01.23	01.11.20	CH
schnudergof	08.12.22	13.08.20	CH
schnudergof	13.06.22	22.06.20	CH
schnudifudi	07.09.23	15.08.22	CH
schweizerblauervogel	02.08.23	17.03.21	CH
schwiizchiste	16.08.21	19.10.16	CH
schwizbestidemokratieduweish	27.08.23	22.02.21	CH
schwizerkniff	28.07.23	28.10.18	CH
secondomeme	10.07.23	17.06.16	CH
sexgruesel	27.08.23	01.05.17	CH
shababs_drainen	25.08.23	03.05.20	CH
shitpostauto	20.04.23	12.06.22	CH
shitposts_zueri	0	N/A	N/A
shreklicher_duennschiss	30.05.23	22.08.22	CH
slimettos	22.05.23	25.02.20	CH

Account name	Latest post	First Post	Language
softundhaessig	16.07.23	10.09.21	CH
sonicfan666	29.08.23	01.05.18	CH
souhuendin	07.09.23	19.02.21	CH
sprachrohr.57	16.02.22	14.05.20	CH
srfarchiv	23.08.23	12.04.21	CH
staernsee	18.12.22	18.12.21	CH
stewia2046	04.09.23	17.11.17	CH
stuebis	26.02.23	03.04.22	CH
suisseromandelibre	07.09.23	19.11.18	FR
swisshood	24.11.22	20.03.20	CH
swissmeme	07.09.23	06.07.13	CH
swissurferssuck	05.09.23	17.11.20	EN
szene_isch_berset	02.12.21	13.01.21	CH
szene_isch_szene	29.01.23	01.10.20	CH
taetschgring	23.08.23	12.08.20	CH
ultras.berset	21.03.23	11.02.21	CH
urner_memelord	0	N/A	CH
vierezwenzgerpackanker	07.11.22	16.08.20	CH
wiichaeller	24.04.20	04.11.16	CH
worb_isch_szene	07.04.22	25.01.21	CH
zapfememes	25.08.23	14.11.20	CH
zeigmaubuebbi	08.10.20	03.08.20	CH
zhabamemes	19.04.23	25.12.21	CH
znueninaehmems	07.04.23	07.09.16	CH
zruegg_iz_deadend	28.07.23	05.10.22	CH
zurichartmemes	06.07.23	12.09.20	EN
zwetschgememes	17.08.23	23.06.21	CH

12. Appendix C: List of Corpus Accounts

From the compiled list of 113 accounts, 34 accounts fit the account criteria for the corpus. In the table below, you will find an overview of these accounts. I have downloaded all image posts up to September 7, 2023 (“Total posts”) for each account. The number of posts fitting the content criteria is noted in the second column (“Total posts Lockdown +1y”). Finally, the table shows when the first feed post was posted on the account.

Account	Total posts	Posts Lock-down +1y	First post
@bundesrat.ch	140	76	28.12.2020
@chline_hutzu	740	419	21.10.2020
@chnoeitoeif_im_schissdraeck	661	377	19.07.2020
@draindler.page	1533	955	26.01.2020
@gagugauge	217	40	06.12.2020
@hajdgenoss	879	78	13.04.2014
@hajdi.ch	628	133	24.01.2017
@hetsno.memes	268	130	29.04.2020
@jesus.nr1	5112	1097	08.11.2015
@lauericheib69	953	106	31.08.2020
@linkefotzen	1441	268	25.01.2021
@loesch.ch	673	264	23.02.2019
@mmp_memes	67	42	04.03.2020
@mondhausi	1995	925	26.07.2020
@muetersduemmst_official	162	163	19.10.2020
@pouletbruchthirni	338	98	18.02.2021
@sadmemeeschwiiz	135	43	21.03.2020
@salzmann.tinu	260	153	30.08.2020
@samanthathic	128	53	13.06.2018
@schnaebrmemes	92	64	01.11.2020
@schwizbestidemokratieduweish	10	11	22.02.2021
@schwizerkniff	208	59	28.10.2018
@secondomeme	1211	65	17.06.2016
@sexgruesel	123	56	01.05.2017
@slimettos	137	34	25.02.2020
@sonicfan666	193	53	01.05.2018
@souhuendin	565	73	19.02.2021
@stewia2046	128	86	17.11.2017
@swissmeme	5788	585	06.07.2013
@szene_isch_szene	468	71	01.10.2020
@taetschgring	367	299	12.08.2020
@ultras.berset	67	40	11.02.2021
@zapfememes	179	2	14.11.2020
@znueninaehmems	3639	542	07.09.2016
Total	29505	7428	

“Lowkey, we’re all comrades by oath” meme by @chline_hutzu. Date unknown

13. Declaration of Independence

I hereby confirm that I have written this master's thesis personally and only with the help of the sources listed in the notes and that I have labeled verbatim quotations and paraphrases as such. This also applies to the visual parts of the thesis. The thesis has not yet been submitted to any other examination authority and has not yet been published.

Benedikt Achermann, February 2024, Biel/Bienne, Switzerland